

PELTMG

State Plan for Logistics and Transportation of Minas Gerais

SHORT-TERM Executive Report

VOLUME 3

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Introduction

This document presents the results of the **Short-Term State Plan for Logistics and Transportation of Minas Gerais (PELTMG)**, an essential strategic tool to support planning and decision-making in the transport sector. PELTMG consolidates data, analyses, and models that intend to guide actions by the State Government, municipalities, regulatory agencies, public and private companies, promoting efficient, safe, and sustainable development of transport infrastructure and services in Minas Gerais.

Established by the **State Logistics and Transport Policy**, formalized by the **SEINFRA Resolution No. 41 from November 8th, 2024**, PELTMG is the main document used to structure planning for the sector in the State of Minas Gerais. The policy defines the foundations, principles, objectives, and guidelines for the technical assessment of projects, ensuring a consistent long-term state vision planning of logistics and transport infrastructure.

As a result, an **integrated portfolio of public and private actions** has been formed to enhance road, rail, waterway, airport and pipeline systems, focusing on building a more cohesive transport network, eliminating overlaps and prioritizing interventions with the greatest economic and social impact. The policy was presented at various regional workshops and made available online for public consultation to gather input from civil society.

Coordinated by the **Minas Gerais State Office of Infrastructure, Mobility and Partnerships (SEINFRA/MG)** and developed by the **Minas Gerais Development Company (CODEMGE)**, with technical support from **INFRA S.A.** and the **Dom Cabral Foundation**, the **Short-Term PELTMG** integrates and aligns state, municipal, and federal strategies, eliminating redundancies and promoting more efficient investments in the transport sector.

The **Short-Term PELTMG** focuses on identifying and prioritising **immediate actions** that meet the main demands of the population and stimulate the state's economic activities. This document presents the results of these analyses, translating them into practical guidelines to facilitate the implementation of strategic interventions and the alignment of state actions with regional and sectoral needs.

The **Short-Term State Plan for Logistics and Transportation of Minas Gerais** comprises the following volumes: **1. Full Report; 2. Executive Report; 3. Dashboard**. The first chapter of this report **highlights the key results** of the short-term PELTMG, providing an overview of expected progress and impacts. The **Analysis Portfolio** details the plan's initial portfolio, covering all transport infrastructures included in the PELTMG, both short-term and long-term scopes, establishing the basis for subsequent analyses. Finally, the **Recommended Portfolio** chapter delves into the short-term PELTMG results, emphasizing action prioritisation and presenting strategic recommendations for each managerial portfolio, including impact type and feasibility analysis for each infrastructure group.

Methodological Differentials

Figure 1: Methodological Differentials

The **Short-term PELTMG** incorporates several methodological innovations, as illustrated in Figure 1, to better the efficiency and effectiveness of transport planning and execution. It uses planning as a tool to assess **social, economic, and environmental aspects** and recommend a set of actions. Various indicators were employed to diagnose and assess the individual impact of portfolio projects to achieve the plan's objectives.

The PELTMG is **a pioneer in Brazil in applying the Five Case Model for transport planning**, a methodology developed by the UK Treasury. This ensures that actions proposed by the plan are structured and aligned with the State's strategy, maximising societal benefits, whether they are financially viable and market-attractive, and feasible to implement.

The **data and simulations** in the plan are characterized by being integrated, comprehensive, and intermodal, ensuring systemic analysis. **Big Data** is used to analyse freight and passenger transport across the territory, such as mobile phone data for constructing origin-destination matrix for people and electronic invoice data from the Brazilian Federal Revenue (RFB) for freight matrix. **Advanced simulation models** anticipate transport system behaviour under different scenarios, aiding in defining the most suitable solutions for each context.

To process this data and generate strategic insights **technological parks as well as state-of-the-art software are involved**, with the entire process structured in databases.

Five Case Model applied to Transport Planning

Figure 2: Five Dimensions Model Adapted and Applied to Transport Planning

The Five Case Model is composed of the following cases: **Strategic Case (1)**, **Socioeconomic Case (2)**, **Financial Case (3)**, **Commercial Case (4)**, and **Management Case (5)**. Each of these cases is detailed in Figure 2. The scope of activities encompassed by the **Strategic**, **Socioeconomic**, and **Financial** cases is traditionally applied in transportation planning. That is, these are plans aimed at demonstrating alignment with the State's strategic policies, as well as delivering social, economic, and environmental benefits, and financial feasibility.

Within the **Strategic Case**, strategic alignment is evaluated through a comprehensive review of current legislation related to policies that support the development of key economic sectors in the state of Minas Gerais. This analysis served as the foundation for identifying the state's strategic freight corridors. In addition, for passenger transport, the main interurban mobility corridors were identified based on the hierarchical structure of the Brazilian urban network, as defined in the 2018 Regions of Influence of Cities (REGIC) report published by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE).

The socioeconomic benefits of implementing the subsequent phases are detailed within the **Socioeconomic Case**, as this is the phase in which both the baseline scenario diagnosis and the projection of future scenarios are conducted (the latter to be included in the Long-Term PELT). These analyses are based on a series of indicators that assess the performance of the state of Minas Gerais in relation to the objectives established in the State Policy for Logistics and Transportation.

The **Financial Feasibility** of actions is analysed in the **Financial Case**. Based on primary feasibility studies for the projects in the analysis portfolio, those with the highest potential to be structured as concessions or public-private partnerships (PPPs) are identified, while also highlighting projects to be executed by public management.

The contribution of the **Five Case Model** to transport planning lies primarily in the inclusion of the Commercial and Management Cases in the plan's development process. The **Commercial Case** captures the market interest level in the portfolio from potential investors and financiers before finalising the portfolio.

In the **Management Case**, the feasibility of implementing actions by their probable responsible entities is assessed. Additionally, potential institutional, environmental, and legal risks are evaluated, along with limiting factors such as technical-operational capacity, budgetary constraints, and temporal resource allocation. In this case, the portfolio is subdivided by probable responsible entities within the state government based on the results of the prioritisation.

The results of the short-term PELTMG aims to objectively quantify potential social, economic, and environmental outcomes of implementing the actions, guiding the organisation and prioritisation of the project portfolio. For this purpose, indexes representing each of the Five Cases are considered as explanatory variables.

The classification flow and the meaning of each index are summarised in Figure 3, and the result of each indicator is treated as an independent variable in the classification equation. The coefficients, which determine the importance of each case in the prioritisation process, were defined in regional workshops held in various cities across Minas Gerais. After normalising the results, each project in the portfolio received a score from 0 to 1, and projects are categorised as High, Medium, or Low Impact.

Taking these considerations into account, **Short-Term PELTMG** designs a plan with a holistic vision to ensure successful implementation, guaranteeing the achievement of the established goals and that Minas Gerais secures its benefits.

The **Classification Index (CI)** ranks projects by impact type, represented by the following equation:

$$CI = \lambda_1 C_{\text{Financial}} + \lambda_2 C_{\text{Socioeconomic}} + \lambda_3 C_{\text{Strategic}} + \lambda_4 C_{\text{Commercial}} + \lambda_5 C_{\text{Management}}$$

In which:

- λ_1 - Coefficient corresponding to the weight assigned to the Financial Case;
- $C_{\text{Financial}}$ - Financial Index;
- λ_2 - Coefficient representing the weight attributed to the Socioeconomic Case;
- $C_{\text{Socioeconomic}}$ - Socioeconomic Index;
- λ_3 - Coefficient representing the weight attributed to the Strategic Case;
- $C_{\text{Strategic}}$ - Strategic Index;
- λ_4 - Coefficient representing the weight attributed to the Commercial Case;
- $C_{\text{Commercial}}$ - Commercial Index;
- λ_5 - Coefficient representing the weight attributed to the Management Case ;
- $C_{\text{Management}}$ - Management Index.

5CM PELTMG Application Flow

Figure 3: Application flow of the 5 Case Model in PELTMG – Short Term

1

Summary

PELTMG

Plano Estadual de Logística e Transportes de Minas Gerais

As a **general overview**¹ of the short-term PELTMG portfolio, Figure 1.1 presents the main quantifiers of prioritised projects, distributed by **sector**, **investment type**, and **status**.

Figure 1.1: Short-term PELTMG - Overview

¹In this report, the conversion of monetary values from Brazilian Real to US Dollar was based on the selling exchange rate of R\$ 5.5709 per USD, as reported by the Central Bank of Brazil on 22th July 2025.

1.1. Investments for Decision-Making and Execution by 2026

Figure 1.2: Overview – Investments for Decision-Making and Execution by 2026

The projects addressed in this section constitute one of the main results of the Short-Term PELTMG, as illustrated in Figure 1.2 and Figure 1.3 with the details of the projects. This division includes projects in early maturity stages (i.e., **planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review**) and thus may have various recommended actions based on the portfolio's broad and objective analysis process. These are accompanied by technical justifications for their selection such as those that best contribute to the State's development, in line with the adopted methodology.

Each subsequent phase in the Short-Term PELTMG links a group of projects to their execution steps to ensure implementation. It is emphasised that the actions are not intended to guarantee that investments will be applied or initiated in the 2025–2026 biennium, as each project group—and each project individually—has its own implementation status. Some require project design, while others demand alignment between government entities, among other stages.

The Short-Term PELTMG consolidates, prioritises, and outlines the next steps for advancing priority projects in their implementation process, ensuring continuity and efficiency in infrastructure management.

\$ 24 Bn Total Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

Sector	Subsequent phase	Qty.	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)	Total Investment (%)
Airports	Align priorities (MT/ANTT); Hire project; Search for deployment alternatives	4	0	94,203,275	94,350,751	188,554,026	0.51
Airports	Contract structuring of an Administrative Concession (SUBPPP)	2	0	12,977,899	15,089,594	28,067,494	0.08
Pipelines	Engage with private sector and contract structuring (SUBPPP); Consider sponsored or Cross-subsidised PPP	4	0	2,659,066,741	0	2,659,066,741	7.26
Railways	Align priorities (MT/ANTT); Hire project; Search for deployment alternatives	9	1,549,242,437	7,610,704,786	4,993,171,807	12,603,876,593	34.42
Waterways	Align priorities (MPOR); Hire structuring or project; look for implementation alternatives	1	160,877,978	177,021,986	295,574,555	472,596,541	1.29
Roads	Align priorities (MT/ANTT/DNIT)	15	418,709,655	3,206,056,103	3,366,214,644	6,572,270,747	17.95
Roads	Contract or continue structuring (SUBPPP)	6	50,932,318	6,167,310,965	2,322,431,364	8,489,742,330	23.18
Roads	Contract or continue public implementation (DER-MG)	305	4,962,534	2,841,982,149	178,965,540	3,020,947,690	8.25
Roads	Contract or continue sponsored PPP (SUBPPP)	2	51,341,755	1,838,606,712	746,698,113	2,585,304,825	7.06
Total		348	2,236,066,679	24,607,930,620	12,012,496,370	36,620,426,991	100.00

Figure 1.3: Investments for Decision-Making and Execution by 2026

1.2. Investments for Monitoring and Management Until 2055

Figure 1.4: Overview – Investments for Monitoring and Management Until 2055

The projects in this section, as illustrated in Figure 1.4 and Figure 1.5 comprise those whose investments are already under **procurement or contract awarded** for implementation in Minas Gerais' logistics and transport infrastructure. This includes signed concession contracts already in execution, projects in procurement, or public investments underway for execution starting in 2025.

This is a significant contribution of the Short-Term PELTMG, as it enables more efficient monitoring of infrastructure management. Previously, information on transport infrastructure projects and investments in Minas Gerais was fragmented across institutions and administrative spheres. The PELTMG consolidated and prioritised these projects, making it possible to visualise, track, and steer contracted investments for Minas Gerais.

\$ 26 Bn
Total Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)

Sector	Qty.	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)	Total Investment (%)
Airports	7	1,121,291,662	2,991,349,533	296,790,823	3,288,140,357	5.60
Pipelines	9	0	0	0	0	0.00
Railways	8	2,423,828,267	15,306,404,625	21,620,949,057	36,927,353,682	62.93
Waterways	2	129,555,037	5,168,683	365,597,485	370,766,168	0.63
Roads	138	1,984,962,702	8,432,229,591	9,658,763,646	18,090,993,238	30.83
Total	164	5,659,637,669	26,735,152,433	31,942,101,013	58,677,253,447	100.00

Figure 1.5: Investments for Monitoring and Management Until 2055

1.3. Key Findings

The project portfolio analysis totals **\$ 181 bn**, comprising **\$ 96 bn CAPEX** and **\$ 85 bn OPEX**.

The **State-level Recommended Portfolio** comprises **442 projects (86%)**, totalling **\$ 15 bn** in investments.

The analysis portfolio includes **1,584 projects**, approximately **89% of which are road-related**.

It is recommended that **\$ 46 bn (90%)** of the total value of the **Recommended Portfolio** be financed through private funding, and **\$ 5 bn (10%)** through public funding.

99% of Minas Gerais municipalities are covered by the PELTMG analysis portfolio.

\$ 25 bn in investments are expected to be allocated by 2026 under the Short-Term Portfolio results.

73 logistical corridors are included in the PELTMG analysis.

\$ 26 bn in investments will be monitored until 2055 under the Short-Term Portfolio results.

The **Short-Term Portfolio** anticipates **\$ 51 bn in new investments**, distributed across **512 projects** (roads, railways, airports, waterways, and pipelines).

Significant impacts: **\$ 249 bn in social, economic, and environmental benefits** from the investments.

The **Analysis Portfolio**¹ for each transport sector serves as the initial input for analyses and forecasts, resulting in the **Recommended Portfolio**, the primary output of the planning cycle. Actions are classified as **projects** or **initiatives**, with the goal of modifying properties, components, or the system environment. Only project-type actions were evaluated in the Short-Term PELTMG. The analysis portfolio consists of **works, services, and projects** at various stages, involving both public and private entities. The portfolio results are visualised in Figure 2.1. It is critical to highlight the state-wide perspective of this works/projects portfolio, ensuring planning continuity even with natural adjustments between government cycles.

To build the portfolio, a comprehensive survey of interventions was conducted, primarily with public authorities but also including privately identified actions. Subsequently, an initial screening of the various identified interventions was carried out, aiming to classify them as individual works, developments, or initiatives.

Figure 2.1: Analysis Portfolio Survey

A **Project** is defined as a grouping of one or more works or services within a single sector, assigned to a single responsible entity. It serves as the unit of evaluation and management for the Government of Minas Gerais and other tactical/strategic entities.

A **Work and Service** is a specific individual intervention by sector, status, and infrastructure type that alters the transport system network, aggregated at the tactical level.

Investment Values presented in the Short-Term PELT refer to the financial values reported by the original sources of each project and are updated to the reference month of August 2024. These values will be recalculated and revised within the context of the Long-Term PELT. However, it is important to highlight that, as studies and projects progress in their level of maturity, the estimates become increasingly accurate, more faithfully reflecting the budget required for the execution of the investments.

¹In this report, the conversion of monetary values from Brazilian Real to US Dollar was based on the selling exchange rate of R\$ 5.5709 per USD, as reported by the Central Bank of Brazil on 22th July 2025.

The portfolio survey process was extensively promoted through regional workshops held in Belo Horizonte, Diamantina, Viçosa, Uberlândia, Ipatinga, Divinópolis, and Poços de Caldas during the first half of 2024. To standardise data collection, an online software tool was available for six months, allowing transport specialists, public/private institutions, study groups, and associations to submit works, services, and projects of interest for Minas Gerais.

Surveyed projects are categorised into six sectors: Airports, Pipelines, Railways, Waterways, Ports and Roads. 1,584 projects were identified, encompassing 7,484 works and services at varying maturity levels and administrative spheres (federal, state, municipal) for intercity freight/passenger transport.

This portfolio does not represent the final Recommended Short-Term Portfolio, but served as the basis for project evaluation, classification, and prioritisation.

Table 2.1 shows the investment distribution by sector, while Figure 2.2 displays their geographic locations in Minas Gerais.

Sector	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)	Investment Percentage (%)
Airports	3,314,026,804	609,252,473	3,923,279,278	2.17
Pipelines	6,829,089,735	0	6,829,089,735	3.77
Railways	53,308,276,635	64,466,979,246	117,775,255,882	65.09
Waterways	665,721,158	661,172,040	1,326,893,198	0.73
Ports	164,784,864	16,034,752	180,819,616	0.10
Roads	32,162,807,801	18,754,424,553	50,917,232,354	28.14
Total	96,444,706,999	84,507,863,066	180,952,570,066	100.00

Table 2.1: Total CAPEX/OPEX by Sector

Figure 2.2: Map of projects across all sectors

The regional distribution of transportation infrastructure investments in Minas Gerais reveals significant disparities among sectors, as shown in Table 2.1 and Figure 2.2. The **Railway** sector, which accounts for approximately 55% of total investments, is particularly prominent in the central and eastern regions of the State, where the **railway** network is denser, highlighting the strategic importance of these areas for freight transport. In contrast, **the road sector**, responsible for around 33% of the investments, exhibits broad coverage across all regions, with particular emphasis on corridors connecting Belo Horizonte to the Triângulo Mineiro, the Zona da Mata, and the southern region of the State. This distribution underscores the critical role of the highway network in supporting intermunicipal passenger and freight transport.

Investments in **airport** and **port** infrastructure are concentrated in strategic regions, namely the Metropolitan Region of Belo Horizonte (RMBH) and the southern part of the State, respectively. The **waterway** sector, which receives less than 1% of total funding, is focused on areas near navigable rivers, primarily along the borders with neighboring states.

Detailed portfolio data is available in the **PELTMG Dashboard** under the Overview and Projects sections.

3

Recommended Portfolio

PELTMG

Plano Estadual de Logística e Transportes de Minas Gerais

The prioritisation of projects in the **Short-Term State Plan for Logistics and Transportation of Minas Gerais (PELTMG)**¹ is conducted by sector based on the results of the **Classification Index (CI)**, **feasibility**, **modelling group** and the **number of analysed cases** involved.

The **Classification Index (CI)** categorises projects into **high**, **medium** or **low** impact using a multiple linear regression of variables containing indexes for the five cases analysis, as detailed in the chapter *Five Case Model applied to Transport Planning*.

Financial feasibility is analysed through the **Internal Rate of Return (IRR)**, following the criteria in Table 3.1. The reference **Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)** used was 10.26%, the rate applied to projects structured by SEINFRA/MG.

Interval	Feasibility
$IRR \geq WACC$	High feasibility
$0 \geq IRR > WACC$	Medium feasibility
$IRR < 0$	Low feasibility

Table 3.1: Financial Feasibility

The **modelling group** is an additional classification aimed at grouping similar projects by their infrastructure nature and transport type (freight and/or passengers). These include:

- General case – linear infrastructures;
- General case – point infrastructures;
- Passenger terminals;
- Road projects without revenue expectations;
- Road maintenance;
- Road rehabilitation;
- Freight terminal projects.

Finally, projects were classified by the number of analysed cases. Projects lacking demand data and/or financial feasibility assessments were excluded from the financial and commercial indexes.

Below are the consolidated results by impact, feasibility, and managerial portfolios. Further details on the prioritisation results are available in the **PELTMG Dashboard**, under the "Recommended Portfolio" section.

¹In this report, the conversion of monetary values from Brazilian Real to US Dollar was based on the selling exchange rate of R\$ 5.5709 per USD, as reported by the Central Bank of Brazil on 22th July 2025.

3.1. Impact

Below are the lists and maps of the top 10 projects with the highest **Classification Index (CI)** by sector.

3.1.1. Airports

Table 3.2 lists the 10 airport projects with the highest classification indexes, as illustrated in Figure 3.1 by impact.

Figure 3.1: Top 10 Projects by Impact (Airports)

Project	Source of the Project	Impact	Classification Index
1925 - Aeroporto de Belo Horizonte/Pampulha-MG - Carlos Drummond de Andrade	CODEMGE	High impact	0.54295
997 - Implantação de terminal de passageiros em BH Airport (Confins/MG) - SBCF	ANAC	High impact	0.50825
1037 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto de Pouso Alegre/MG - SNZA	CODEMGE	High impact	0.43139
1050 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Embaixador Walther Moreira Salles (Poços de Caldas/MG) - SBPC	CODEMGE	High impact	0.40622
998 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Tenente Coronel Aviador César Bombonato (Uberlândia/MG) - UDI	ANAC	High impact	0.40297
1000 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Mário Ribeiro (Montes Claros/MG) - MOC	ANAC	High impact	0.35330
1044 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Prefeito Octávio de Almeida Neves (São João del-Rei/MG) - SNJR	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.33639
999 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Mário de Almeida Franco (Uberaba/MG) - UBA	ANAC	Medium impact	0.33528
1042 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Municipal José Figueiredo (Passos/MG) - SNOS	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.33329
1043 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto de Mocimbinho (Jaíba/MG) - SNMK	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.30719

Table 3.2: Top 10 CI - Airports

3.1.2. Pipelines

Table 3.3 lists the 10 pipeline projects with the highest classification indexes, as illustrated in Figure 3.2 by impact.

Figure 3.2: Top 10 Projects by Impact (Pipelines)

Project	Source of the Project	Impact	Classification Index
1886 - Operação do Mineroduto Minas-Rio	CODEMGE	High impact	0.24532
1885 - Operação do Mineroduto Samarco	CODEMGE	High impact	0.19171
714 - Implantação de dutovia em Projeto Dutoviário D2: Construção do Poliduto Regap – Uberaba/MG	PELT 2007	Medium impact	0.18862
993 - Implantação de dutovia em Oleoduto Uberaba/MG - Cuiabá/MT	PIO 2022	Medium impact	0.17599
715 - Implantação de dutovia em Projeto Dutoviário D3: Construção do Poliduto Regap – Governador Valadares/MG	PELT 2007	Medium impact	0.17589
1884 - Operação de dutovia em ORBEL II	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.16753
1888 - Operação de dutovia em ORBEL I	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.16740
996 - Implantação de dutovia em Gasoduto Linhares/ES - Gov. Valadares/MG	PIG 2022	Medium impact	0.15699
995 - Implantação de dutovia em Gasoduto Jacutinga/MG - Uberaba/MG	PIG 2022	Low impact	0.15152
1883 - Operação do Mineroduto Vale Tapira-Uberaba	CODEMGE	Low impact	0.15027

Table 3.3: Top 10 CI - Pipelines

3.1.3. Railways

Table 3.4 lists the 10 railway projects with the highest classification indexes, as illustrated in Figure 3.3 by impact.

Figure 3.3: Top 10 Projects by Impact (Railways)

Project	Source of the Project	Impact	Classification Index
80 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário na MRS Logística S.A.	ANTT	High impact	0.51429
113 - Renovação da Concessão da Malha Centro-Leste (Ferrovia Centro-Atlântica S.A.) - FCA	ANTT	High impact	0.48515
739 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 48C - Extensão da Ferrovia do Aço, do Terminal de Otávio Dapieve (Município de Rio Acima) até Belo Horizonte (Caetano Furquim)	PEF 2021	High impact	0.43226
100 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Estrada de Ferro Vitória a Minas (Vale S.A.) - EFVM	ANTT	High impact	0.41665
973 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Itabirito/MG a Santa Rita Durão/MG - Shortline Ferroviária	SEINFRA	High impact	0.41196
57 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Renovação da Concessão da Malha Sudeste (MRS Logística S.A.)	ANTT	High impact	0.39398
108 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Malha Centro-Leste (Ferrovia Centro-Atlântica S.A.) - FCA	ANTT	High impact	0.39038
85 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Sete Lagoas/MG a Anápolis/GO	ANTT	Medium impact	0.37776
747 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 105C Ferroanel da Região Metropolitana de Belo Horizonte - 2	PEF 2021	Medium impact	0.37157
737 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em FC 47A Capitão Eduardo (Município de Santa Luzia) - Pedreira do Rio das Velhas (Município de Sabará)	PEF 2021	Medium impact	0.36040

Table 3.4: Top 10 CI - Railways

3.1.4. Waterways and Ports

Table 3.5 lists the top projects in waterways and ports with the highest classification indexes, as illustrated in Figure 3.4 by impact.

Figure 3.4: Top 10 Projects by Impact (Waterways and Ports)

Project	Source of the Project	Impact	Classification Index
122 - Manutenção de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do Rio Paraná	INFRASA	High impact	0.48184
721 - Ampliação do Corredor do Rio São Francisco a partir da Represa de Três Marias	PELT 2007	High impact	0.27450
722 - Manutenção de trecho hidroviário em Projeto Hidroviário H2: Criação do Corredor do Rio Grande entre o Lago de Furnas e o Pontal do Triângulo	PELT 2007	High impact	0.26148
723 - Manutenção de trecho hidroviário em Projeto Hidroviário H3: Criação do Corredor do Rio Paranaíba entre o Lago da Emborcação e o Pontal do Triângulo	PELT 2007	High impact	0.22069
1926 - Balsa Manga-Matias Cardoso	CODEMGE	Medium impact	0.18507
48 - Implantação de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do São Francisco - Pirapora/MG a Ibotirama/BA	PHE	Medium impact	0.18332
1006 - Operação de trecho hidroviário em Lago de Furnas	FURNAS	Medium impact	0.17953
709 - Implantação e Operação - Porto Campo do Meio	DNIT	High impact	0.17082
710 - Implantação e Operação - Porto Carmo do Rio Claro	DNIT	High impact	0.17002
707 - Obras de Melhoramento dos Terminais-MG	DNIT	High impact	0.15985

Table 3.5: Top 10 CI - Waterways and Ports

3.1.5. Roads

Table 3.6 lists the 10 road projects with the highest classification indexes, as illustrated in Figure 3.5 by impact.

Figure 3.5: Top 10 Projects by Impact (Roads)

Project	Source of the Project	Impact	Classification Index
105 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-116/465/493/RJ/MG (EcoRioMinas)	ANTT	High impact	0.50637
123 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG/SP (Autopista Fernão Dias)	ANTT	High impact	0.46095
67 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG (BH - Governador Valadares)	ANTT	High impact	0.45721
796 - Lote 9 - Zona da Mata	SEINFRA	High impact	0.41332
65 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG/RJ (Concer)	ANTT	High impact	0.38893
141 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/ES/MG	ANTT	Medium impact	0.37534
56 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-060/153/262/DF/GO/MG (Concebra)	ANTT	Medium impact	0.37337
46 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-116 / 251 / MG: Contratação BNDES (1600 km) - Lote 1	ANTT	Medium impact	0.35907
140 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/MG - PAC	INFRASA	High impact	0.35049
81 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-135/MG (Itacarambi - Divisa MG/BA)	PNL 2035	High impact	0.35037

Table 3.6: Top 10 CI - Roads

3.2. Feasibility

Table 3.7 displays the total investment **sector** and **feasibility** (**high**, **medium**, and **low**). Below are the lists and maps of the top 10 projects with the highest **feasibility** results, divided by sector.

Sector	Feasibility	Total Investment (\$)
Airports	High feasibility	604,124,862
Airports	Medium feasibility	186,489,457
Airports	Low feasibility	2,094,223,831
Railways	High feasibility	34,811,757,559
Railways	Medium feasibility	54,699,010,565
Railways	Low feasibility	2,910,470,401
Waterways	High feasibility	843,362,710
Roads	High feasibility	16,347,783,083
Roads	Medium feasibility	19,417,943,781

Table 3.7: Total Investment by Sector and Feasibility

3.2.1. Airports

Table 3.8 lists the 10 airport projects with the highest IRR values, as illustrated in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Feasibility Map of Top 10 IRR - Airports

Project	Source of the Project	TIR (%)	Feasibility	Total Investment (\$)
997 - Implantação de terminal de passageiros em BH Airport (Confins/MG) - SBCF	ANAC	12.68	High feasibility	604,124,862
1925 - Aeroporto de Belo Horizonte/Pampulha-MG - Carlos Drummond de Andrade	CODEMGE	8.10	Medium feasibility	158,421,963
1037 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto de Pouso Alegre/MG - SNZA	CODEMGE	4.25	Medium feasibility	12,957,880
1050 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Embaixador Walther Moreira Salles (Poços de Caldas/MG) - SBPC	CODEMGE	0.15	Medium feasibility	15,109,613
1044 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Prefeito Octávio de Almeida Neves (São João del-Rei/MG) - SNJR	CODEMGE	-3.01	Low feasibility	67,302,516
1042 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Municipal José Figueiredo (Passos/MG) - SNOS	CODEMGE	-4.32	Low feasibility	15,526,839
1051 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Usiminas (Santana do Paraíso/MG) - SBIP	CODEMGE	-4.95	Low feasibility	62,928,631
998 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Tenente Coronel Aviador César Bombonato (Uberlândia/MG) - UDI	ANAC	-5.12	Low feasibility	618,424,589
1046 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Brigadeiro Antônio Cabral (Divinópolis/MG) - SNDV	CODEMGE	-9.83	Low feasibility	67,099,201
1052 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Coronel Altino Machado (Governador Valadares/MG) - SBGV	CODEMGE	-12.75	Low feasibility	41,337,105

Table 3.8: Top 10 IRR - Airports

3.2.2. Railways

Table 3.9 lists the 10 railway projects with the highest IRR values, as illustrated in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Feasibility Map of Top 10 IRR - Railways

Project	Source of the Project	TIR (%)	Feasibility	Total Investment (\$)
737 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em FC 47A Capitão Eduardo (Município de Santa Luzia) - Pedreira do Rio das Velhas (Município de Sabará)	PEF 2021	41.48	High feasibility	219,509,459
113 - Renovação da Concessão da Malha Centro-Leste (Ferrovia Centro-Atlântica S.A.) - FCA	ANTT	23.80	High feasibility	4,612,849,115
80 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário na MRS Logística S.A.	ANTT	23.80	High feasibility	5,860,723,543
100 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Estrada de Ferro Vitória a Minas (Vale S.A.) - EFVM	ANTT	19.21	High feasibility	5,014,443,965
97 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em São Mateus/ES a Ipatinga/MG	ANTT	17.14	High feasibility	1,915,520,713
82 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Barra de São Francisco/ES a Brasília/DF	ANTT	16.55	High feasibility	2,705,862,473
85 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Sete Lagoas/MG a Anápolis/GO	ANTT	15.21	High feasibility	0
107 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Ferrovia Norte-Sul Tramo Central e Extensão Sul (Rumo Malha Central S.A.) - FNSTC	ANTT	15.18	High feasibility	3,470,435,678
973 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Itabirito/MG a Santa Rita Durão/MG - Shortline Ferroviária	SEINFRA	14.98	High feasibility	83,044,174
736 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 46B Grão Mogol - Janaúba - Entrocamento com a FIOEL	PEF 2021	13.83	High feasibility	4,562,109,781

Table 3.9: Top 10 IRR - Railways

3.2.3. Waterways

Table 3.10 lists the 2 waterway projects with the highest IRR values, as illustrated in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Feasibility Map of Top 2 IRR - Waterways

Project	Source of the Project	TIR (%)	Feasibility	Total Investment (\$)
122 - Manutenção de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do Rio Paraná	INFRASA	24.68	High feasibility	353,076,449
48 - Implantação de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do São Francisco - Pirapora/MG a Ibotirama/BA	PHE	14.34	High feasibility	472,596,541
1926 - Balsa Manga-Matias Cardoso	CODEMGE	13.21	High feasibility	17,689,719

Table 3.10: Top 2 IRR - Waterways

3.2.4. Roads

Table 3.11 lists the 10 road projects with the highest IRR values, as illustrated in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Feasibility Map of Top 10 IRR - Roads

Project	Source of the Project	TIR (%)	Feasibility	Total Investment (\$)
971 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Estrada Pico-Fábrica	SEINFRA	17.28	High feasibility	33,379,813
67 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG (BH - Governador Valadares)	ANTT	16.46	High feasibility	415,546,022
105 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-116/465/493/RJ/MG (EcoRioMinas)	ANTT	16.46	High feasibility	1,667,364,606
123 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG/SP (Autopista Fernão Dias)	ANTT	16.46	High feasibility	924,970,433
65 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG/RJ (Concer)	ANTT	16.46	High feasibility	290,707,284
140 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/MG - PAC	INFRAASA	14.86	High feasibility	0
792 - Lote 5 - Itapecerica-Lagoa da Prata	SEINFRA	14.34	High feasibility	3,131,736,752
130 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG - PAC	INFRAASA	14.04	High feasibility	123,842,522
141 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/ES/MG	ANTT	12.94	High feasibility	847,022,326
960 - Pavimentação de trecho rodoviário de Ouro Branco/MG até Santo Antônio do Leite/MG	CODEMGE	12.31	High feasibility	84,904,368

Table 3.11: Top 10 IRR - Roads

3.3. Managerial Portfolios

This section presents the results by **managerial portfolio**. A total of **18 managerial portfolios** were defined, grouped by expected responsible entities, as shown in Table 3.12, with sector subdivisions in Figure 3.10. The following subsections detail the criteria adopted for selecting each portfolio and present the list of projects with impact classification, financial data, and maps.

Figure 3.10: Investment Percentage by Sector by Responsible Party

Portfolio	Expected Responsible	Number of Projects	Total Investment (\$)
Carteira para Concessão e Parcerias Público-Privadas	SUBPPP	15	14,234,777,933
Portfolio for Investment Prospecting	SUBMOB	71	70,539,530,109
Portfolio for Contract Awarded Projects	ARTEMIG	9	6,583,402,694
Portfolio for Publicly Executed Projects on State Roads	DER-MG	417	3,939,969,700

Table 3.12: Quantity and Investment by Portfolio

In certain portfolios, the financial values of some projects appear as zero. This may occur for two reasons:

(1) The values were excluded from the investment composition because the projects are considered competing ventures. Competing ventures refer to projects within the same sector that vie for the same infrastructure and comprise similar works and services. In such cases, the project with the lower investment value was excluded from the portfolio to present a more conservative estimate.

(2) The financial value of the project was not available, and no estimate was provided for the associated works and services. This was observed particularly in projects within the pipeline sector and in certain airport terminals.

Additionally, estimated amounts to be spent between 2025 and 2026 are provided for each project included in the portfolio.

3.3.1. Portfolio for Concessions and Public-Private Partnerships

PPP1 Portfolio: State Road Projects for contracting or continuation of Standard Concession structuring

Table 3.13 lists the projects in PPP1 Portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.11. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Roads;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High;
- **Impact:** High, medium, and low.

Figure 3.11: Map of Projects in PPP1 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	2	444,669,435	454,159,386	50,932,318	898,828,821
Medium impact	3	3,598,826,856	815,882,879	0	4,414,709,736
High impact	1	2,123,814,673	1,052,389,098	0	3,176,203,772
Total	6	6,167,310,965	2,322,431,364	50,932,318	8,489,742,330

Table 3.13: Projects in PPP1 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed in Table 3.14, the recommended course of action is the engagement or continuation of the structuring process for a conventional concession.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
796 - Lote 9 - Zona da Mata	0,41332	High impact	11.02	High feasibility	2,123,814,673	1,052,389,098	3,176,203,772
792 - Lote 5 - Itapecerica-Lagoa da Prata	0,33195	Medium impact	14.34	High feasibility	2,782,941,626	348,795,126	3,131,736,752
797 - Lote 10 - Noroeste	0,32148	Medium impact	11.02	High feasibility	790,586,321	407,482,293	1,198,068,615
960 - Pavimentação de trecho rodoviário de Ouro Branco/MG até Santo Antônio do Leite/MG	0,31267	Medium impact	12.31	High feasibility	25,298,908	59,605,459	84,904,368
794 - Lote 7 - Ouro Preto	0,24663	Low impact	11.07	High feasibility	434,128,859	431,320,148	865,449,008
971 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Estrada Pico-Fábrica	0,25811	Low impact	17.28	High feasibility	10,540,575	22,839,238	33,379,813
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	6,167,310,965	2,322,431,364	8,489,742,330

Table 3.14: PPP1 Portfolio

PPP2 Portfolio: State Road Projects for contracting or continuation of Sponsored Concession structuring

Table 3.15 The Table presents the projects included in the PPP2 portfolio², as illustrated in Figure 3.12. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Roads;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** Medium;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.12: Map of Projects in PPP2 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	2	1,838,606,712	746,698,113	51,341,755	2,585,304,825
Total	2	1,838,606,712	746,698,113	51,341,755	2,585,304,825

Table 3.15: Projects in PPP2 Portfolio by Impact

²PPP2 Portfolio includes high and medium-impact projects, but prioritisation resulted only in medium-impact projects.

For the projects listed in Table 3.16, the subsequent phase is to contract or continue structuring the sponsored concession.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
791 - Lote 4 - São João del-Rei	0,32809	Medium impact	8.77	Medium feasibility	1,308,618,021	504,939,810	1,813,557,831
795 - Lote 8 - Vetor Norte	0,29422	Medium impact	10.03	Medium feasibility	529,988,690	241,758,302	771,746,993
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	1,838,606,712	746,698,113	2,585,304,825

Table 3.16: PPP2 Portfolio

PPP3 Portfolio: Airport Projects for contracting or continuation of Administrative Concession structuring

Table 3.17 lists the projects in PPP3 Portfolio³, as illustrated in Figure 3.13. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Airports;
- **Government Level:** State and Municipal;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High and medium;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.13: Map of Projects in PPP3 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
High impact	2	12,977,899	15,089,594	0	28,067,494
Total	2	12,977,899	15,089,594	0	28,067,494

Table 3.17: Projects in PPP3 Portfolio by Impact

³PPP3 Portfolio includes high and medium-impact projects, but prioritisation resulted only in high-impact projects.

For the projects listed in Table 3.18, the recommended course of action is the engagement or continuation of the structuring process for an administrative concession.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1037 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto de Pouso Alegre/MG - SNZA	0,43139	High impact	4.25	Medium feasibility	5,413,083	7,544,797	12,957,880
1050 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Embaixador Walther Moreira Salles (Poços de Caldas/MG) - SBPC	0,40622	High impact	0.15	Medium feasibility	7,564,816	7,544,797	15,109,613
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	12,977,899	15,089,594	28,067,494

Table 3.18: PPP3 Portfolio

PPP4 Portfolio: Waterway Projects for contracting or continuation of Standard or Sponsored Concession structuring

Table 3.19 lists the projects in PPP4 Portfolio⁴, as illustrated in Figure 3.14. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Waterways;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, and low;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.14: Map of Projects in PPP4 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	1	177,021,986	295,574,555	160,877,978	472,596,541
Total	1	177,021,986	295,574,555	160,877,978	472,596,541

Table 3.19: Projects in PPP4 Portfolio by Impact

⁴PPP4 Portfolio includes high and medium-impact projects, but prioritisation resulted only in medium-impact projects.

For the projects listed in table 3.20, the subsequent phase is to contract or continue structuring the sponsored concession.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
48 - Implantação de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do São Francisco - Pirapora/MG a Ibotirama/BA	0,18332	Medium impact	14.34	High feasibility	177,021,986	295,574,555	472,596,541
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	177,021,986	295,574,555	472,596,541

Table 3.20: PPP4 Portfolio

PPP5 Portfolio: Pipeline Projects for contracting or continuation of Standard or Sponsored Concession structuring

Table 3.21 lists the projects in PPP5 Portfolio⁵, as illustrated in Figure 3.15. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Pipelines;
- **Government Level:** Federal, State, Municipal, and Undefined;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, and unevaluated;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.15: Map of Projects in PPP5 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	4	2,659,066,741	0	0	2,659,066,741
Total	4	2,659,066,741	0	0	2,659,066,741

Table 3.21: Projects in PPP5 Portfolio by Impact

⁵PPP5 Portfolio includes high and medium-impact projects, but prioritisation resulted only in medium-impact projects.

For the projects listed in Table 3.22, the subsequent phase is to contract or continue structuring the sponsored concession.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
714 - Implantação de dutovia em Projeto Dutoviário D2: Construção do Poliduto Regap – Uberaba/MG	0,18862	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	35,900,841	0	35,900,841
715 - Implantação de dutovia em Projeto Dutoviário D3: Construção do Poliduto Regap – Governador Valadares/MG	0,17589	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	16,155,378	0	16,155,378
993 - Implantação de dutovia em Oleoduto Uberaba/MG - Cuiabá/MT	0,17599	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	1,780,093,364	0	1,780,093,364
996 - Implantação de dutovia em Gasoduto Linhares/ES - Gov. Valadares/MG	0,15699	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	826,917,156	0	826,917,156
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	2,659,066,741	0	2,659,066,741

Table 3.22: PPP5 Portfolio

3.3.2. Portfolio for Investment Prospecting

Plan1 Portfolio: Federal Road Projects for investment priority alignment

Table 3.23 lists the projects in Plan1 Portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.16. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Roads;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, and low;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.16: Map of Projects in Plan1 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	11	1,716,594,334	2,417,132,832	221,791,884	4,133,727,166
High impact	4	1,489,461,769	949,081,811	196,917,770	2,438,543,581
Total	15	3,206,056,103	3,366,214,644	418,709,655	6,572,270,747

Table 3.23: Projects in Plan1 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ⁶ in Table 3.24, it is recommended to align priorities with the responsible entities for their management.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
81 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-135/MG (Itacarambi - Divisa MG/BA)	0,35037	High impact	9.05	Medium feasibility	726,077,830	398,831,769	1,124,909,600
140 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/MG - PAC	0,35049	High impact	14.86	High feasibility	0	0	0
130 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG - PAC	0,34721	High impact	14.04	High feasibility	69,257,658	54,584,863	123,842,522
112 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-251/MG	0,29673	High impact	9.06	Medium feasibility	694,126,280	495,665,178	1,189,791,459
68 - Lotes 8 e 9 - BR-367/MG	0,23977	Medium impact	7.77	Medium feasibility	440,359,645	314,454,225	754,813,871
46 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-116 / 251 / MG: Contratação BNDES (1600 km) - Lote 1	0,35907	Medium impact	11.88	High feasibility	308,045,947	947,693,994	1,255,739,942
60 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-154/MG	0,16626	Medium impact	7.29	Medium feasibility	47,145,089	25,896,616	73,041,705
50 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/495/MG/RJ	0,32698	Medium impact	11.17	High feasibility	41,972,870	397,375,529	439,348,399
75 - Lote 40 - BR-479/DF/GO/MG	0,20045	Medium impact	6.76	Medium feasibility	329,259,404	226,499,838	555,759,243
70 - Lote 19 - BR-464/497/MG	0,22229	Medium impact	8.44	Medium feasibility	260,824,245	185,116,466	445,940,711
69 - Lote 10 - BR-265/MG	0,26090	Medium impact	9.04	Medium feasibility	274,216,771	312,366,170	586,582,942
106 - Lote 11 - BR-251/DF/GO/MG	0,22510	Medium impact	9.30	Medium feasibility	0	0	0
121 - Implantação do Terminal Rodoviário de Santa Juliana	0,07737	Medium impact	0.00	Medium feasibility	697,821	0	697,821
131 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-251/MG - PAC	0,22982	Medium impact	9.23	Medium feasibility	0	0	0
138 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-364/MG - PAC	0,23503	Medium impact	9.62	Medium feasibility	14,072,537	7,729,991	21,802,528
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	3,206,056,103	3,366,214,644	6,572,270,747

Table 3.24: Plan1 Portfolio

⁶The following projects are considered competing ventures: 46, 112, and 131; 99 and 140; 106 and 112.

Plan2 Portfolio: Federal Railway Projects for investment priority alignment

Table 3.25 lists the projects in Plan2 Portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.17. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Railways;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, and low;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.17: Map of Projects in Plan2 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	6	2,955,964,885	3,394,135,448	0	6,350,100,334
High impact	3	4,654,739,900	1,599,036,358	1,549,242,437	6,253,776,258
Total	9	7,610,704,786	4,993,171,807	1,549,242,437	12,603,876,593

Table 3.25: Projects in Plan2 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ⁷ in Table 3.26, it is recommended to align priorities with the responsible entities, contract the project, or seek viable implementation alternatives where applicable.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
113 - Renovação da Concessão da Malha Centro-Leste (Ferrovia Centro-Atlântica S.A.) - FCA	0,48515	High impact	23.80	High feasibility	3,389,304,660	1,223,544,455	4,612,849,115
739 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 48C - Extensão da Ferrovia do Aço, do Terminal de Otávio Dapieve (Município de Rio Acima) até Belo Horizonte (Caetano Furquim)	0,43226	High impact	2.06	Medium feasibility	1,183,026,373	374,856,594	1,557,882,968
973 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Itabirito/MG a Santa Rita Durão/MG - Shortline Ferroviária	0,41196	High impact	14.98	High feasibility	82,408,866	635,308	83,044,174
733 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 45B Anápolis/GO - Unai - Pirapora - Prudente de Moraes / Sete Lagoas/MG	0,35417	Medium impact	10.25	Medium feasibility	2,575,985,200	2,948,575,621	5,524,560,822
737 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em FC 47A Capitão Eduardo (Município de Santa Luzia) - Pedreira do Rio das Velhas (Município de Sabará)	0,36040	Medium impact	41.48	High feasibility	16,935,144	202,574,314	219,509,459
738 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 48A, Extensão da Ferrovia do Aço, do Terminal de Otávio Dapieve (Município de Rio Acima) até Belo Horizonte (Caetano Furquim)	0,32160	Medium impact	-4.62	Low feasibility	0	0	0
746 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 105A Ferroanel da Região Metropolitana de Belo Horizonte - 1	0,30456	Medium impact	5.05	Medium feasibility	363,044,540	242,985,512	606,030,052
85 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Sete Lagoas/MG a Anápolis/GO	0,37776	Medium impact	15.21	High feasibility	0	0	0
747 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em FC 105C Ferroanel da Região Metropolitana de Belo Horizonte - 2	0,37157	Medium impact	2.49	Medium feasibility	0	0	0
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	7,610,704,786	4,993,171,807	12,603,876,593

Table 3.26: Plan2 Portfolio

⁷The following projects are considered competing ventures: 85 and 733; 738 and 739; 746 and 747.

Plan3 Portfolio: Federal Airport Projects for investment priority alignment

Table 3.27 lists the projects in Portfolio Plan3, as illustrated in Figure 3.18. The selection criteria were:

- **Sector:** Airports;
- **Government Level:** Federal, State, and Municipal;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** Low;
- **Impact:** High and medium.

Figure 3.18: Map of Projects in Plan3 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	4	94,203,275	94,350,751	0	188,554,026
Total	4	94,203,275	94,350,751	0	188,554,026

Table 3.27: Projects in Plan3 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed in Table 3.28, it is recommended to align priorities with the competent entities, contract the project, or seek implementation alternatives where applicable.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1038 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto de Ubá/MG - SNUB	0,29896	Medium impact	-15.30	Low feasibility	27,873,452	14,922,586	42,796,039
1042 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Municipal José Figueiredo (Passos/MG) - SNOS	0,33329	Medium impact	-4.32	Low feasibility	7,982,042	7,544,797	15,526,839
1044 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Prefeito Octávio de Almeida Neves (São João del-Rei/MG) - SNJR	0,33639	Medium impact	-3.01	Low feasibility	31,360,832	35,941,683	67,302,516
1051 - Ampliação de terminal de passageiros do Aeroporto Usiminas (Santana do Paraíso/MG) - SBIP	0,29875	Medium impact	-4.95	Low feasibility	26,986,947	35,941,683	62,928,631
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	94,203,275	94,350,751	188,554,026

Table 3.28: Plan3 Portfolio

3.3.3. Portfolio for Contracted Projects

Reg/Monit1 Portfolio: State Road Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for contract management and implementation monitoring

Table 3.29 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit1 portfolio⁸, as illustrated in Figure 3.19. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Road;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.19: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit1 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	2	1,020,338,483	1,490,617,664	382,317,421	2,510,956,147
Medium impact	3	1,630,847,851	1,328,344,999	335,000,421	2,959,192,850
High impact	2	863,592,832	536,574,121	67,675,464	1,400,166,953
Total	7	3,514,779,166	3,355,536,784	784,993,307	6,870,315,951

Table 3.29: Projects in the Reg/Monit1 Portfolio by Impact

⁸The Reg/Monit1 portfolio includes projects of high, medium, and low impact; however, the prioritization process resulted exclusively in the selection of high- and medium-impact projects.

For the projects listed in Table 3.30, the subsequent phase is to prioritise monitoring their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
842 - AB Nascentes das Gerais - MG-050/BR-265/BR-491	0,26085	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	863,592,832	350,381,100	1,213,973,933
830 - Concessão Tergip	0,15455	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	186,193,020	186,193,020
788 - Lote 1 - Triângulo Mineiro	0,28626	Medium impact	9.25	Medium feasibility	568,753,676	496,939,958	1,065,693,634
789 - Lote 2 - Sul de Minas	0,31326	Medium impact	10.32	High feasibility	954,052,227	662,615,068	1,616,667,296
831 - Rodoanel Metropolitano de Belo Horizonte	0,32488	Medium impact	11.20	High feasibility	108,041,947	168,789,971	276,831,919
790 - Lote 3 - Varginha Furnas	0,27554	Low impact	9.25	Medium feasibility	461,817,075	459,698,807	921,515,882
829 - Eco 135 - BR-135/MG-231/LMG-754	0,27332	Low impact	9.41	Medium feasibility	558,521,407	1,030,918,857	1,589,440,264
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	3,514,779,166	3,355,536,784	6,870,315,951

Table 3.30: Reg/Monit1 Portfolio

Reg/Monit2 Portfolio: Federal Road Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for implementation monitoring

Table 3.31 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit2 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.20. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Road;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.20: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit2 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	2	240,090,940	1,031,072,577	22,928,583	1,271,163,517
Medium impact	12	3,330,744,722	1,994,740,607	345,503,618	5,325,485,330
High impact	5	647,562,553	3,057,443,875	477,978,562	3,705,006,428
Total	19	4,218,398,215	6,083,257,060	846,410,764	10,301,655,276

Table 3.31: Projects in the Reg/Monit2 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ⁹ in Table 3.32, the recommended course of action is to monitor their execution with priority.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
67 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG (BH - Governador Valadares)	0,45721	High impact	16.46	High feasibility	24,986,161	390,559,861	415,546,022
65 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG/RJ (Concer)	0,38893	High impact	16.46	High feasibility	10,485,704	280,221,579	290,707,284
105 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-116/465/493/RJ/MG (EcoRioMinas)	0,50637	High impact	16.46	High feasibility	349,980,745	1,317,383,860	1,667,364,606
123 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-381/MG/SP (Autopista Fernão Dias)	0,46095	High impact	16.46	High feasibility	25,004,969	899,965,464	924,970,433
132 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-365/MG - PAC	0,26802	High impact	6.72	Medium feasibility	237,104,972	169,313,109	406,418,081
56 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-060/153/262/DF/GO/MG (Concebra)	0,37337	Medium impact	7.69	Medium feasibility	1,493,761,155	665,956,601	2,159,717,757
128 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/GO/MG - Rota dos Cristais	0,32209	Medium impact	9.04	Medium feasibility	708,396,848	767,785,533	1,476,182,382
63 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-367/MG	0,15789	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
135 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-265/MG - PAC	0,20253	Medium impact	5.73	Medium feasibility	46,944,374	25,786,365	72,730,739
137 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-356/MG - PAC	0,22533	Medium impact	6.79	Medium feasibility	46,256,209	25,408,358	71,664,568
129 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-262/MG - Rota do Zebu	0,30540	Medium impact	7.55	Medium feasibility	0	0	0
134 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-135/MG - PAC	0,23875	Medium impact	7.93	Medium feasibility	41,563,990	22,830,940	64,394,931
139 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-367/MG - PAC	0,23408	Medium impact	7.86	Medium feasibility	89,749,717	49,299,175	139,048,893
991 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-040/MG - Belo Horizonte/MG a Juiz de Fora/MG - Via Mineira	0,17409	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	893,028,813	437,673,631	1,330,702,444
1034 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-265/MG entre Jacuí e Alpinópolis	0,16813	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1033 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-135/MG entre São João das Missões e Manga	0,15998	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1035 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na BR-440/MG	0,16554	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	11,043,612	0	11,043,612
103 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-364/365/MG/GO (Ecovias do Cerrado)	0,22776	Low impact	3.55	Medium feasibility	73,884,106	563,542,564	637,426,671
104 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na BR-050/GO/MG (Eco050)	0,27637	Low impact	6.76	Medium feasibility	166,206,833	467,530,012	633,736,846
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	4,218,398,215	6,083,257,060	10,301,655,276

Table 3.32: Reg/Monit2 Portfolio

⁹identified as competing ventures (56 and 129; 63 and 139; 135 and 1034; 134 and 1033).

Reg/Monit3 Portfolio: Federal Railway Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for implementation monitoring

Table 3.33 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit3 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.21. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Rail;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.21: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit3 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	3	980,106,559	6,658,708,646	91,056,087	7,638,815,205
Medium impact	1	1,756,461,267	1,713,974,411	32,260,562	3,470,435,678
High impact	4	12,569,836,798	13,248,265,999	2,300,511,616	25,818,102,798
Total	8	15,306,404,625	21,620,949,057	2,423,828,267	36,927,353,682

Table 3.33: Projects in the Reg/Monit3 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ¹⁰ in Table 3.34, the subsequent phase is to monitor their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
57 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Renovação da Concessão da Malha Sudeste (MRS Logística S.A.)	0,39398	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	44,300,122	6,948,907,825	6,993,207,947
80 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário na MRS Logística S.A.	0,51429	High impact	23.80	High feasibility	3,595,248,154	2,265,475,389	5,860,723,543
108 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Malha Centro-Leste (Ferrovia Centro-Atlântica S.A.) - FCA	0,39038	High impact	7.91	Medium feasibility	7,100,491,636	849,235,704	7,949,727,341
100 - Ampliação de trecho ferroviário em Estrada de Ferro Vitória a Minas (Vale S.A.) - EFVM	0,41665	High impact	19.21	High feasibility	1,829,796,885	3,184,647,080	5,014,443,965
107 - Implantação de trecho ferroviário em Ferrovia Norte-Sul Tramo Central e Extensão Sul (Rumo Malha Central S.A.) - FNSTC	0,33430	Medium impact	15.18	High feasibility	1,756,461,267	1,713,974,411	3,470,435,678
52 - Manutenção/Recuperação do Pátio Ferroviário de Santos Dumont/MG	0,14575	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
78 - Adequação da Linha Férrea em Juiz de Fora/MG	0,19432	Low impact	0.00	Medium feasibility	54,180,586	6,658,708,646	6,712,889,233
114 - Resolução de Conflitos Urbanos Ferroviários	0,21483	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	925,925,972	0	925,925,972
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	15,306,404,625	21,620,949,057	36,927,353,682

Table 3.34: Reg/Monit3 Portfolio

¹⁰The following projects are considered competing ventures: 52, 57, and 80.

Reg/Monit4 Portfolio: State Airport Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for contract management and implementation

Table 3.35 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit4 portfolio¹¹, as illustrated in Figure 3.22. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Airport;
- **Government Level:** State and Municipal;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.22: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit4 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	1	0	0	0	0
High impact	2	35,257,113	123,164,850	10,794,391	158,421,963
Total	3	35,257,113	123,164,850	10,794,391	158,421,963

Table 3.35: Projects in the Reg/Monit4 Portfolio by Impact

¹¹The Reg/Monit4 portfolio includes projects of high, medium, and low impact; however, the prioritization process resulted exclusively in the selection of high- and medium-impact projects.

For the projects listed ¹² in Table 3.36, the subsequent phase is to monitor execution or assume management.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1067 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Prefeito Octávio De Almeida Neves (São João Del Rei/MG) - SNJR	0,21535	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1925 - Aeroporto de Belo Horizonte/Pampulha-MG - Carlos Drummond de Andrade	0,54295	High impact	8.10	Medium feasibility	35,257,113	123,164,850	158,421,963
1066 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Regional da Zona da Mata (Goianá/MG) - SBZN	0,20329	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	35,257,113	123,164,850	158,421,963

Table 3.36: Reg/Monit4 Portfolio

¹²The financial values of these projects were not available.

Reg/Monit5 Portfolio: Federal Airport Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for implementation monitoring

Table 3.37 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit5 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.23. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Airport;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.23: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit5 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	1	697,861,653	30,498,378	321,973,283	728,360,031
High impact	3	2,258,230,766	143,127,595	788,523,986	2,401,358,361
Total	4	2,956,092,419	173,625,973	1,110,497,270	3,129,718,393

Table 3.37: Projects in the Reg/Monit5 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed in table 3.38, the subsequent phase is to monitor their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
997 - Implantação de terminal de passageiros em BH Airport (Confins/MG) - SBCF	0,50825	High impact	12.68	High feasibility	550,531,907	53,592,955	604,124,862
998 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Tenente Coronel Aviador César Bombonato (Uberlândia/MG) - UDI	0,40297	High impact	-5.12	Low feasibility	564,831,634	53,592,955	618,424,589
1000 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Mário Ribeiro (Montes Claros/MG) - MOC	0,35330	High impact	-13.64	Low feasibility	1,142,867,225	35,941,683	1,178,808,908
999 - Operação de terminal de passageiros em Aeroporto Mário de Almeida Franco (Uberaba/MG) - UBA	0,33528	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	697,861,653	30,498,378	728,360,031
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	2,956,092,419	173,625,973	3,129,718,393

Table 3.38: Reg/Monit5 Portfolio

Reg/Monit6 Portfolio: Federal Waterway and Port Projects contract awarded or under procurement, for implementation monitoring

Table 3.39 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit6 portfolio¹³, as illustrated in Figure 3.24. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Waterway and Port;
- **Government Level:** Federal;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.24: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit6 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
High impact	1	2,438,931	350,637,517	129,555,037	353,076,449
Total	1	2,438,931	350,637,517	129,555,037	353,076,449

Table 3.39: Projects in the Reg/Monit6 Portfolio by Impact

¹³The Reg/Monit6 portfolio includes projects of high, medium, and low impact; however, the prioritization process resulted exclusively in the selection of high-impact projects.

For the projects listed in Table 3.40, the subsequent phase is to prioritise monitoring their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
122 - Manutenção de trecho hidroviário na Hidrovia do Rio Paraná	0,48184	High impact	24.68	High feasibility	2,438,931	350,637,517	353,076,449
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	2,438,931	350,637,517	353,076,449

Table 3.40: Reg/Monit6 Portfolio

Reg/Monit7 Portfolio: Pipeline projects contract awarded or under procurement, for contract management and implementation monitoring

Table 3.41 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit7 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.25. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Pipeline;
- **Government Level:** Federal, State, Municipal, and Undefined;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.25: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit7 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	5	0	0	0	0
Medium impact	2	0	0	0	0
High impact	2	0	0	0	0
Total	9	0	0	0	0

Table 3.41: Projects in the Reg/Monit7 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ¹⁴ in Table 3.42, the subsequent phase is to prioritise monitoring their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1886 - Operação do Mineroduto Minas-Rio	0,24532	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1885 - Operação do Mineroduto Samarco	0,19171	High impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1884 - Operação de dutovia em ORBEL II	0,16753	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1888 - Operação de dutovia em ORBEL I	0,16740	Medium impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1883 - Operação do Mineroduto Vale Tapira-Uberaba	0,15027	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1887 - Operação de dutovia em GASBEL - II (Trecho 2: Tapinhoá/Rio das Flores - Betim)	0,14505	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1889 - Operação de dutovia em OSBRA 20 POL (REPLAN - Senador Canedo)	0,12970	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1890 - Operação de dutovia em GASBEL (REDUC/REGAP)	0,14720	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
1891 - Operação de dutovia em Paulínia-Jacutinga	0,12040	Low impact	Not applicable	Not applicable	0	0	0
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	0	0	0

Table 3.42: Reg/Monit7 Portfolio

¹⁴The financial values of these projects were not available.

Reg/Monit8 Portfolio: Pipeline projects contract awarded or under procurement, for contract management and implementation monitoring

Table 3.43 displays the projects in the Reg/Monit8 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.26. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Ports and Waterway;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** High, medium, low, or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.26: Map of Projects in the Reg/Monit8 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Medium impact	1	2,729,752	14,959,967	0	17,689,719
Total	1	2,729,752	14,959,967	0	17,689,719

Table 3.43: Projects in the Reg/Monit8 Portfolio by Impact

For the projects listed ¹⁵ in Table 3.44, the subsequent phase is to prioritise monitoring their execution.

Project	CI	Impact	TIR (%)	Feasibility	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1926 - Balsa Manga-Matias Cardoso	0,18507	Medium impact	13.21	High feasibility	2,729,752	14,959,967	17,689,719
Total	-----	-----	-----	-----	2,729,752	14,959,967	17,689,719

Table 3.44: Reg/Monit8 Portfolio

¹⁵The financial values of these projects were not available.

3.3.4. Portfolio for Publicly Executed Projects on State Roads

RodoPub1 Portfolio: Road projects for contracting or continuation of studies and designs for publicly funded implementation

Table 3.45 displays the projects in the RodoPub1 portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.27. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Road;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Planning phase, feasibility study, design phase, or preliminary review;
- **Feasibility:** Low feasibility or not evaluated;
- **Impact:** High.

Figure 3.27: Map of Projects in the RodoPub1 Portfolio

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
High impact	305	2,841,982,149	178,965,540	4,962,534	3,020,947,690
Total	305	2,841,982,149	178,965,540	4,962,534	3,020,947,690

Table 3.45: Projects in the RodoPub1 Portfolio by Impact

Due to the size of the RodoPub1 portfolio, the classification results were divided by primary intervention, as indicated in Table 3.46, which will be detailed in the following subsections.

Main Intervention	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)	Total Investment (%)
Ampliação de OAE	1	136,502,164	178,965,540	315,467,704	10.44
Expansion of road section	2	730,996,642	0	730,996,642	24.20
Road Section Implementation	9	900,093,511	0	900,093,511	29.80
Construction of special engineering structures	53	68,091,961	0	68,091,961	2.25
Road Section Maintenance	239	1,006,297,868	0	1,006,297,868	33.31
Total	305	2,841,982,149	178,965,540	3,020,947,690	100.00

Table 3.46: Summary by Intervention for the RodoPub1 Portfolio

For the projects listed in Tables 3.47 to 3.58 the recommendation is to procure or continue execution, as applicable.

RodoPub1 Portfolio - Construction of special engineering structures

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
248 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio São Francisco - Entr. MGC-135 (Manga) - Porto Matias e Variante na Rodovia MG-401	0,15699	High impact	27,293,941	0	27,293,941
686 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Itanguá do trecho Senador Modestino - Itamarandiba	0,15665	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
547 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Ribeirão Salitre do trecho Presidente Olegário - Galena	0,15654	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
622 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Pedra Branca do trecho Entr. BR-116 - Pedra Azul	0,15649	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
435 - Implantação de OAE na MG-406 (Rubim a Rio do Prado)	0,15639	High impact	17,297	0	17,297
676 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Jaboticaba do trecho Arinos - Unai	0,15603	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
678 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Uruçuia do trecho Arinos - Unai	0,15603	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
677 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o rib. Capas do trecho Arinos - Unai	0,15603	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
621 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Santa Rosa do trecho Pedra Grande - Pedra Azul	0,15590	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
610 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Ribeirão Japy do trecho Guaxupé - São Pedro da União	0,15578	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
638 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre cór. São Félix do trecho Santa Margarida - Entr. BR-262	0,15543	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
530 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Ribeirão de Areia do trecho Camilinho - Rio Paraúna	0,15514	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
529 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Capim Branco do trecho Ent. Alvorada de Minas - Ent. Itapanhoacanga	0,15361	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
635 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Pau Alto do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15343	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
617 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre rib. Cangalha do trecho Unai - Paracatu	0,15341	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
290 - Implantação de OAE: Serro - Milho Verde (Pte. Rib. Três Barras)	0,15327	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
623 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Santo Antônio do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15310	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
626 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Santaninha do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15299	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
624 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio São Jacinto do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15299	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
625 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Santana do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15299	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
627 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Todos os Santos do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15299	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
628 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Canabrava do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,15299	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
636 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Preto II do trecho Itaipé - Santa Cruz	0,15287	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
680 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio São Francisco do trecho Pedras de Maria Cruz - Januária	0,15040	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
681 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Poeira do trecho Pedras de Maria Cruz - Januária	0,15040	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
688 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o rib. Cercado do trecho Caratinga - Brasilândia de Minas	0,15037	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
687 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o rib. Tronco do trecho Caatinga - Brasilândia de Minas	0,15037	High impact	826,077	0	826,077

Table 3.47: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Construction of special engineering structures (Part 1)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
616 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Engenho Velho do trecho Paracatu - João Pinheiro	0,15033	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
583 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre cór. Barra Nova do trecho Felisburgo - Jequitinhonha	0,15023	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
288 - Implantação de OAE: Porto Buriti - Entr. BR-040 (João Pinheiro)	0,15020	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
679 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Uruçuia do trecho Buritis - Formoso	0,14997	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
328 - Implantação de OAE: LMG-714 (Entr. BR-040 a Porto Diamante)	0,14978	High impact	28,565	0	28,565
533 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Bicudo do trecho Ent. para Diamante - Rio Bicudo	0,14926	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
632 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio São Domingos do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14886	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
629 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Laje do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14870	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
631 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Uruçu do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14870	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
630 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Quejeme do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14870	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
684 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Cór. Olaria do trecho Senador Modestino - Itamarandiba	0,14795	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
683 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio São Domingos do trecho Senador Modestino - Itamarandiba	0,14795	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
685 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Cór. Veneno do trecho Senador Modestino - Itamarandiba	0,14795	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
579 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Medeira do trecho Rubim - Rio do Prado	0,14782	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
582 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre rib. Bandeira do trecho Rubim - Rio do Prado	0,14782	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
674 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio São Francisco do trecho Entr. BR-352 - Pompéu	0,14746	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
581 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Alcobaça do trecho Machacalis - Umburatiba	0,14739	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
634 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Ene do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14642	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
633 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Sangue do trecho Nanuque - Teófilo Otoni	0,14642	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
585 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Jequitinhonha do trecho Araçuaí - Coronel Murta	0,14559	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
580 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Córrego Pam Pam do trecho Machacalis - Águas Formosas	0,14559	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
682 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Itamarandiba do trecho Entr. Capetinha - Itamarandiba	0,14518	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
584 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre Rio Araçuaí do trecho Araçuaí - Virgem da Lapa	0,14461	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
586 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o cór. Morgado do trecho Araçuaí - Novo Cruzeiro	0,14439	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
392 - Implantação de OAE: Capinópolis - Entr. BR-365 (Ituiutaba)	0,14335	High impact	274,343	0	274,343
615 - Implantação de OAE: Ponte sobre o Rio Escuro do trecho BR-040 - Vazante	0,14231	High impact	826,077	0	826,077
Total	-----	-----	68,091,961	0	68,091,961

Table 3.48: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Construction of special engineering structures (Part 2)

RodoPub1 Portfolio - Expansion and Construction of Road Sections

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
833 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Redes Locais	0,21029	High impact	123,222,549	0	123,222,549
835 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Entre Redes	0,19986	High impact	103,366,315	0	103,366,315
29 - Lote 16 - Uberaba / Iturama	0,19242	High impact	500,032,578	0	500,032,578
866 - Implantação de trecho Rodoviário entre a divisa com Goiás e Montalvânia/MG	0,19144	High impact	361,100,147	0	361,100,147
1011 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário na CMG-497	0,19125	High impact	230,964,064	0	230,964,064
837 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Anel Urbano	0,18814	High impact	51,962,799	0	51,962,799
907 - Implantação de trecho Rodoviário entre Pindorama/BA e Montezuma/MG	0,18723	High impact	146,215,138	0	146,215,138
1010 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Anel Viário de Ipatinga/MG	0,18701	High impact	30,807,379	0	30,807,379
916 - Implantação de trecho Rodoviário entre São Gonçalo do Rio Abaixo/MG e Nova Era/MG	0,18444	High impact	31,929,886	0	31,929,886
836 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Centralidade Norte	0,17906	High impact	50,271,921	0	50,271,921
418 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Virgem da Lapa - Entr. LMG-677	0,15526	High impact	1,217,374	0	1,217,374
Total	-----	-----	1,631,090,154	0	1,631,090,154

Table 3.49: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Expansion and Construction of Road Sections

RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
31 - Lote 18 - Montes Claros	0,18667	High impact	415,067,063	0	415,067,063
18 - Lote 5 - Pouso Alegre	0,18205	High impact	0	0	0
1138 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-259 - Entr. MG-314 (Conceição de Tronqueiros) a Sabinópolis (início trecho urbano) - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,17184	High impact	10,388,250	0	10,388,250
1265 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-259 - Sabinópolis (início trecho urbano) a início perímetro urbano de Gouveia) - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,16663	High impact	15,324,262	0	15,324,262
1136 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-040 - Crucilândia a Brumadinho - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,16605	High impact	2,556,834	0	2,556,834
1787 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-460 - Lambari (fim trecho urbano) a Entr. MG-347 (Carmo de Minas) - 10ª CRG - Varginha	0,16578	High impact	5,103,861	0	5,103,861
1715 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-758 - Entr. MG-C259 à Entr. BR-381 - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16571	High impact	8,674,350	0	8,674,350
1343 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-179 - Entr. BR-491 (Alfenas) à Entr. BR-459 (p/ Pouso Alegre) - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,16560	High impact	5,905,691	0	5,905,691
1137 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-120 - Entr. p/ M dos Homens (div. 38/02 CRG) a div. 02/12 - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,16496	High impact	6,027,251	0	6,027,251
1649 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-635 - final perímetro urbano Gameleiras à Entr. MG-C122 C (p/Mato Verde) - 32ª CRG - Janaúba	0,16475	High impact	2,560,660	0	2,560,660
1750 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-010 - Conceição do Mato Dentro à Entr. MG-229 (Sapo) (div. 02/08 CRG) - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,16474	High impact	8,743,216	0	8,743,216
1612 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-353 - Entr. BR-040 B (p/ Rio de Janeiro) a Rio Preto (div. MG/RJ) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,16453	High impact	4,068,129	0	4,068,129
1267 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-259 - Ponte sobre o Rio Paraúna (div. 8/9 CRG) à Entr. BR-040 (Felixlândia) - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,16452	High impact	9,101,746	0	9,101,746
1681 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-202 - Entr. MG-402 (p/ Uruçuaia) à Entr. MG-400/CMG-479 (Farofão) - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,16427	High impact	4,423,470	0	4,423,470
1713 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-181 - Riachinho (div. 36/39 CRG) a Ribeirão Canastra - 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,16422	High impact	8,415,107	0	8,415,107
1737 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-425 - Entr. BR-381 (Coronel Fabriciano) à Entr. LMG-760 (Cava Grande) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16365	High impact	1,565,714	0	1,565,714
1383 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-356 à Ouro Preto A - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,16362	High impact	1,185,866	0	1,185,866
1826 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-356 à Ouro Preto B - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,16362	High impact	86,874	0	86,874
408 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Cangalhas - Boqueirão	0,16362	High impact	10,781,022	0	10,781,022
1124 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-440 - Entr. BR-356 (Cachoeira do Campo) à Entr. MG-030 (Engenheiro Correia) - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,16362	High impact	276,509	0	276,509
1717 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-760 - Entr. MG-425 (Cava Grande) à Entr. MG-320 (p/São José Goiabal) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16359	High impact	3,954,914	0	3,954,914
1802 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-434 - Entr. BR-381 (p/ Belo Horizonte) a início perímetro urbano Itabira - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,16358	High impact	1,693,286	0	1,693,286
1658 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-635 - final perímetro urbano Santo Antônio do Retiro (div. 32/34 CRG) à Entr. BR-342(B) Montezuma - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,16337	High impact	696,946	0	696,946
1799 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-779 - Itabira (Parque de Exposições) a João Monlevade - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,16335	High impact	919,000	0	919,000
1591 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-111 à Caparaó - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,16328	High impact	480,772	0	480,772
1551 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-610 - Divisópolis a Pedra Azul - 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,16317	High impact	790,263	0	790,263
1464 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-381 - div. ES/MG à Entr. BR-259(A) (São Vitor) - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,16291	High impact	16,359,454	0	16,359,454

Table 3.50: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 1)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1592 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-474 à Taparuba - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,16269	High impact	306,479	0	306,479
1722 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-381 a Antônio Dias - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16265	High impact	291,026	0	291,026
1720 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-232 - Entr. BR-381 (Ipatinga) a Braúnas (div. 40/2 CRG) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16249	High impact	3,199,838	0	3,199,838
1125 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-442 - Entr. BR-040 (p/ Congonhas) a Belo Vale - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,16247	High impact	2,244,539	0	2,244,539
1163 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-238 - Entr. BR-040 (div. 1/3 CRG) à Entr. MG-060 (Maravilhas) - 3ª CRG - Pará de Minas	0,16238	High impact	2,168,532	0	2,168,532
1645 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MGC-122 a Mamonas - 32ª CRG - Janaúba	0,16237	High impact	265,437	0	265,437
1189 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-030 - km 106,5 (div. 1/4 CRG) à Entr. BR-040 - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,16221	High impact	1,081,987	0	1,081,987
1307 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-232 - Morro do Pilar a Gruta Nossa Entr. MG-010 (Alto do Palácio) - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,16216	High impact	1,028,288	0	1,028,288
1261 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-220 - Rodeador a Rodeador - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,16200	High impact	0	0	0
1391 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-120 - acesso Cajuri) a Dom Silvério - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,16169	High impact	10,778,903	0	10,778,903
1719 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-123 - Entr. BR-381 (João Monlevade) à Entr. MG-C120 - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16158	High impact	1,861,536	0	1,861,536
1663 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-626 - Entr. BR-251 (p/BR-116) à Entr. BR-251 (p/ Montes Claros) - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,16152	High impact	3,334,897	0	3,334,897
1689 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-892 - Entr. BR-135 (Montalvânia) a final perímetro urbano Juvenília (divisa MG/BA) - 37ª CRG - Janaúba	0,16143	High impact	1,442,456	0	1,442,456
1505 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-455 - Entr. BR-262 (Campo Florido) a Ponte sobre o Rio Cabaçal - 25ª CRG - Uberaba	0,16139	High impact	3,395,097	0	3,395,097
1684 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-479 - Chapada Gaúcha à Entr. MG-202 A (Arinos) - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,16129	High impact	3,225,835	0	3,225,835
1580 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-111 a Faria Lemos - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,16128	High impact	208,861	0	208,861
1745 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-010 - Estação BRT/MOVE São Gabriel a Venda Nova (Viaduto Vilarinho) - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,16120	High impact	4,617,037	0	4,617,037
1397 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-223 - Entr. BR-365 (p/ Patrocínio) à Entr. BR-050 A (div. 18/11CRG) - 18ª CRG - Monte Carmelo	0,16099	High impact	7,820,628	0	7,820,628
1730 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-458 a Aeroporto Regional do Vale do Aço - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,16078	High impact	137,747	0	137,747
1836 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-262 - Entr. p/ Cachoeira do Brumado à Entr. MG-129 - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,16069	High impact	9,752,820	0	9,752,820
1690 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-135 - Entr. BR-030(B) (Montalvânia) a Manga (início perímetro urbano) - 37ª CRG - Janaúba	0,16058	High impact	1,768,732	0	1,768,732
1202 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-135 - Pedro Teixeira (início trecho urbano) a Pedro Teixeira (início trecho desafetado) - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,16051	High impact	0	0	0
1589 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-482 a início perímetro urbano Ponte Alta - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,16049	High impact	157,200	0	157,200
1597 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-834 - Carangola à Entr. MG-111 (Carangola) - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,16048	High impact	0	0	0
1557 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-217 - Entr. BR-116 (p/ Teófilo Otoni) a Malacacheta (div. 28/38 CRG) - 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,16037	High impact	8,258,859	0	8,258,859
1691 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-135 - início perímetro urbano Itacarambi (início calçamento) a Lontra - 37ª CRG - Janaúba	0,16027	High impact	7,383,119	0	7,383,119
1162 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-060 - Esmeraldas (Córrego São José) a Pompéu Velho (div. 3/35 CRG) - 3ª CRG - Pará de Minas	0,16026	High impact	4,522,353	0	4,522,353

Table 3.51: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 2)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1310 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-135 - Lontra a div. 13/6 CRG - 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,15972	High impact	4,829,836	0	4,829,836
1735 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-320 - Entr. BR-381 (p/ Cel Fabriciano) a final perímetro urbano Mariléria - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15956	High impact	931,932	0	931,932
1744 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-816 - Entr. LMG-511 (Alto da Mangabeira) à Entr. MG-010 (Serra do Cipó) - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15947	High impact	960,641	0	960,641
1877 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-816 - início perímetro urbano Santana do Riacho à Entr. LMG-511 (Alto Mangabeira) - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15946	High impact	0	0	0
1388 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-129 a Santa Rita de Ouro Preto - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15939	High impact	0	0	0
1680 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-181 - Entr. MG-202 (P/Arinos) a Riachinho (div. 36/39 CRG) - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,15936	High impact	735,918	0	735,918
1479 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. LMG-788 a Alvarenga - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15921	High impact	256,006	0	256,006
186 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MG-634 (p/ Almenara) - Mata Verde	0,15913	High impact	11,711,783	0	11,711,783
1869 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-126 - Mar de Espanha a Mar de Espanha - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15907	High impact	9,141,060	0	9,141,060
1667 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-235 - Entr. LMG-794 A (p/E. do Indaiá) a Serra da Saudade - 35ª CRG - Abaeté	0,15904	High impact	607,461	0	607,461
1490 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-848 - São Pedro da União a São Pedro da União - 24ª CRG - Passos	0,15902	High impact	0	0	0
1605 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-393 - div. RJ/MG (Pirapetinga) à Entr. BR-116(A) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15880	High impact	5,277,372	0	5,277,372
1687 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-604 - Entr. LMG-603 (p/ Januária) a início perímetro urbano de Bonito de Minas - 37ª CRG - Januária	0,15870	High impact	1,547,900	0	1,547,900
1321 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-202 - Entr. BR-135 B (p/ Mirabela) à Entr. MG-161 - 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,15867	High impact	5,993,479	0	5,993,479
1547 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-632 - entr BR-116 a Cachoeira Pajeú - 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,15866	High impact	633,026	0	633,026
1544 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-614 - Entr. LMG-610 (p/ Mata Verde) à Entr. BR-116 (Divisa Alegre) - 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,15864	High impact	1,051,915	0	1,051,915
407 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Bonfinópolis de Minas - Brasília de Minas (km 60 ao 121)	0,15844	High impact	7,829,076	0	7,829,076
1770 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-679 - Entr. BR-365 a Claro dos Poções - 6ª CRG - Montes Claros	0,15830	High impact	130,984	0	130,984
1494 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-344 - divisa MG/SP à Entr. MG-050 (P/ Itaú de Minas) - 24ª CRG - Passos	0,15820	High impact	7,621,960	0	7,621,960
1350 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-267 - Entr. MG-179/453 (Machado) à Entr. BR-146(A) - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,15816	High impact	2,322,630	0	2,322,630
1135 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-030 - Entr. BR-356(B) (BH Shopping) a Rio Acima - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15812	High impact	2,051,862	0	2,051,862
1759 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-383 - Entr. LMG-501 (contorno de São Brás do Suaçuí) à Entr. MG-270 - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15810	High impact	852,080	0	852,080
1727 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - km 7,2 a Parque Estadual do Rio Doce - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15806	High impact	376,836	0	376,836
168 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-365 (Pirapora) - Entr. BR-135 (Corinto)	0,15796	High impact	20,800,272	0	20,800,272
1556 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-211 - Entr. BR-116 a Novo Cruzeiro (div. 28/38 CRG) - 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,15795	High impact	5,115,679	0	5,115,679
1140 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-736 - Entr. MGC-120 à Entr. MG-117 (P/ Coluna) - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,15786	High impact	1,369,674	0	1,369,674
1209 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-275 - Entr. MG-124 (Brás Pires) a Senhora de Oliveira (fim do trecho urbano) - 5ª CRG - Ubá	0,15777	High impact	659,452	0	659,452

Table 3.52: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 3)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1707 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-251 a início perímetro urbano de Dom Bosco - 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,15771	High impact	469,445	0	469,445
1731 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. CMG-120/BR-120 a Nova Era (início perímetro urbano) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15771	High impact	74,766	0	74,766
1728 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-381 a Nova Era - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15771	High impact	452,704	0	452,704
1678 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-628 - Entr. MG-202 (Farofa) à Entr. MG-188 - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,15749	High impact	6,494,586	0	6,494,586
1153 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-229 - Dom Joaquim à Entr. MG-010 (Sapo) - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,15745	High impact	3,478,819	0	3,478,819
1831 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-120 a Cajuri - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15733	High impact	0	0	0
1710 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-667 - Entr. MG-181 (Brasilândia) a Santa Fé de Minas - 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,15731	High impact	4,137,630	0	4,137,630
1268 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-754 - AMG-0910 (Curvelo) a início do trecho concessionado - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15723	High impact	673,131	0	673,131
1273 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. CMG-135 (A) (p/ Montes Claros) à Entr. CMG-259 (B) (Curvelo) - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15723	High impact	1,202,056	0	1,202,056
1274 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. AMG-0910 (Curvelo) à Entr. CMG-259 (Curvelo) - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15723	High impact	97,612	0	97,612
1650 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-635 - Entr. MG-C122 A (p/Mato Verde) a final perímetro urbano Santo Antônio do Retiro (DIV 32/34 CRG) - 32ª CRG - Janaúba	0,15711	High impact	1,577,354	0	1,577,354
1545 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-618 - Entr. BR-116 à Entr. p/ Águas Vermelhas (B) - 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,15708	High impact	585,900	0	585,900
1563 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-342 - Entr. MG-211 (Carai) à Entr. BR-116(A) (Catuji) - 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,15694	High impact	1,426,582	0	1,426,582
1481 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-458 - Tarumirim à Entr. BR-116(A) (Taruçu) - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15691	High impact	1,997,997	0	1,997,997
1152 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-229 - Entr. BR-120 (Senhora do Porto) a Senhora do Porto - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,15691	High impact	0	0	0
1463 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-259 - Entr. BR-116/451 à Entr. MG-314 (Conceição de Tronqueiros) - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15686	High impact	1,538,319	0	1,538,319
1358 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-270 - Entre Rios de Minas à Entr. BR-381 - 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,15657	High impact	8,357,294	0	8,357,294
1736 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-320 - início perímetro urbano São José do Goiabal à Entr. BR-262 (p/ Rio Casca) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15657	High impact	2,530,333	0	2,530,333
1706 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-214 - Senador Modestino Gonçalves a Senador M.Gonçalves (div. 38/8 CRG) - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15656	High impact	0	0	0
1319 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-161 - Entr. MG-202 a Rio São Francisco (div. 13/33 CRG) - 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,15652	High impact	182,291	0	182,291
1113 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-813 - Entr. BR-040 à Entr. MG-040 - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15651	High impact	410,563	0	410,563
1702 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-211 - Novo Cruzeiro (div. 28/38 CRG) a Setubinha - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15650	High impact	2,033,757	0	2,033,757
1190 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-129 - Ouro Branco (div. 17/4 CRG) a Conselheiro Lafaiete - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15648	High impact	2,018,738	0	2,018,738
1575 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-108 a Durandé (B) - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15645	High impact	0	0	0
1248 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-187 - Entr. MG-230 (Salitre de Minas) à Entr. BR-262 - 7ª CRG - Araxá	0,15644	High impact	6,611,702	0	6,611,702
1184 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-482 - Piranga à Entr. BR-040 (Conselheiro Lafaiete) - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15642	High impact	8,538,068	0	8,538,068
1793 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MGC-262 a Brumal - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,15639	High impact	0	0	0

Table 3.53: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 4)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1415 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-460 - final perímetro urbano Munhoz à Entr. BR-381 - 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,15638	High impact	1,426,285	0	1,426,285
1315 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-403 - São João da Ponte a Ibiracatu - 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,15632	High impact	2,565,616	0	2,565,616
1436 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-439 - Entr. BR-354 (p/ Arcos) à Entr. MG-170 (p/ Pimenta) - 20ª CRG - Formiga	0,15627	High impact	1,373,375	0	1,373,375
1686 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-479 - Chapada Gaúcha a Pandeiros - 37ª CRG - Januária	0,15625	High impact	0	0	0
1588 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116 a Orizânia - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15621	High impact	0	0	0
1471 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-788 - Entr. p/ Alvarenga a Tarumirim - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15613	High impact	2,028,756	0	2,028,756
1320 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-202 - São João da Ponte a Entr. BR-135 A (Japonvar) - 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,15613	High impact	1,350,700	0	1,350,700
1250 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-230 - Entr. p/R Parnaíba (div. 14/7 CRG) à Entr. MG-187 (div. 7/18 CRG) - 7ª CRG - Araxá	0,15601	High impact	3,290,535	0	3,290,535
1212 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-452 - Entr. MGC-265/MG-448 à Entr. BR-040 - 5ª CRG - Ubá	0,15596	High impact	3,675,042	0	3,675,042
1145 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-232 - Dolores de Guanhões a Entr. BR-120 A - 2ª CRG - Guanhões	0,15595	High impact	616,260	0	616,260
1144 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-780 - Entr. MGC-259 à Entr. BR-120 - 2ª CRG - Guanhões	0,15591	High impact	846,500	0	846,500
1620 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-874 - Entr. BR-267 (p/ Bicas) à Entr. BR-040 B - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15590	High impact	1,441,803	0	1,441,803
1711 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-680 - Entr. MG-181 (Brasilândia de Minas) - km 0 a Rio Paracatu (DIV 26CRG) - km 20- 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,15590	High impact	61,090	0	61,090
1355 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-843 - Entr. BR-369 à Entr. BR-381 - 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,15585	High impact	1,281,195	0	1,281,195
1542 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-251 - Pedra Azul à Entr. BR-116(A) - 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,15578	High impact	2,459,455	0	2,459,455
1606 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-494 - Andrelândia à Entr. BR-267 (Araguaína) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15577	High impact	1,062,569	0	1,062,569
1412 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-173 - Sapucaí Mirim à divisa SP/MG - 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,15572	High impact	358,281	0	358,281
1147 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. LMG-736 a São José do Jacuri - 2ª CRG - Guanhões	0,15568	High impact	33,301	0	33,301
1146 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. LMG-736 a São José do Jacuri - 2ª CRG - Guanhões	0,15568	High impact	53,300	0	53,300
1617 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-040 a Santana do Deserto - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15568	High impact	135,424	0	135,424
1348 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-267 a Paiolinho - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,15564	High impact	419,365	0	419,365
1278 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-220 - Monjolos (div. 8/9 CRG) à Entr. BR-040 (p/ Três Marias) - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15560	High impact	3,493,917	0	3,493,917
1604 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-383 - Madre de Deus de Minas à Entr. p/São Vicente de Minas (B) (div. 30/10 CRG) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15559	High impact	2,298,458	0	2,298,458
1682 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-400 - Entr. CMG-479 (Farofão)/MG-202 a Formoso - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,15556	High impact	7,648,479	0	7,648,479
1732 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-120 - entr MG-123 (P/ Alvinópolis) à Entr. BR-381(B) (p/Nova Era) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15551	High impact	1,086,946	0	1,086,946
1763 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-356 - Entr. BR-120(B) (Coimbra) a Ervália - 5ª CRG - Ubá	0,15545	High impact	678,568	0	678,568
1405 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na BR-459 - fim per. urbano de Itajubá à div. MG/SP - 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,15535	High impact	0	0	0

Table 3.54: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 5)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1196 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-443 a acesso bairro 1º de Maio - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15535	High impact	54,924	0	54,924
1827 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-262 a Diogo de Vasconcelos - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15534	High impact	125,855	0	125,855
1581 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116 a Caputira - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15534	High impact	658,796	0	658,796
1615 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-353 a Belmiro Braga - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15531	High impact	674,769	0	674,769
1768 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-611 - Entr. BR-365 a Coração de Jesus - 6ª CRG - Montes Claros	0,15531	High impact	1,234,907	0	1,234,907
1465 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-451 - Marilac à Entr. BR-116(A) - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15518	High impact	1,399,637	0	1,399,637
1251 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-235 - Entr. BR-354 B (div. 14/7 CRG) à Entr. MG-187 (Ibiá) - 7ª CRG - Araxá	0,15512	High impact	2,124,837	0	2,124,837
1708 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-662 - Entr. LMG-664 (p/ Bonfinópolis) a Natalândia - 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,15509	High impact	120,113	0	120,113
177 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Coromandel - Patrocínio	0,15506	High impact	7,290,024	0	7,290,024
1368 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-369 - São Francisco de Paula Oliveira a final perímetro urbano Oliveira - 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,15505	High impact	3,858,402	0	3,858,402
1371 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-335 - Entr. MG-332 B (Bom Sucesso) à Entr. BR-265 (Lavras) - 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,15503	High impact	2,511,086	0	2,511,086
1149 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MGC-120 a São Pedro do Suaçuí - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,15498	High impact	107,845	0	107,845
1156 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-416 - Entr. MGC-120 (p/ Guanhães) a São Pedro do Suaçuí - 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,15498	High impact	18,372	0	18,372
1795 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-129 a Itabira - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,15496	High impact	344,625	0	344,625
1709 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-664 - Entr. p/ Natalândia à Entr. LMG-628 - 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,15496	High impact	1,093,108	0	1,093,108
1309 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-462 - Entr. BR-120/MG-129 a Itabira (bairro Campestre I) - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,15496	High impact	159,573	0	159,573
1446 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-642 - Entr. MGC-367/MG-405 a Santa Maria do Salto - 21ª CRG - Jequitinhonha	0,15491	High impact	834,390	0	834,390
1281 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-383 - Entr. p/São Vicente de Minas (B) (div. 30/10 CRG) à Entr. BR-354(A) (Cruzília) - 10ª CRG - Varginha	0,15490	High impact	6,824,912	0	6,824,912
1449 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-105 - Rio Jequitinhonha (div. 27/21 CRG) a Águas Formosas (div. 21/28 CRG) - 21ª CRG - Jequitinhonha	0,15481	High impact	2,415,013	0	2,415,013
1734 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-820 - final perímetro urbano São Domingos do Prata a Dionísio - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15481	High impact	1,262,160	0	1,262,160
1177 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-252 - Entr. MG-430 (p/Igaratinga) a Araújos (div. 3/20 CRG) - 3ª CRG - Pará de Minas	0,15478	High impact	2,876,360	0	2,876,360
1373 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-817 - Entr. MG-326 (Cláudio Manoel) à Entr. MG-262 - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15474	High impact	0	0	0
1835 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-129 - Mariana à Entr. MG-262/BR-356(A) - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15474	High impact	0	0	0
1379 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-326 - Cláudio Manoel (div. 12/17 CRG) ao fim do trecho pavimentado - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15474	High impact	244,249	0	244,249
1621 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-874 - Entr. BR-040 C (início trecho urbano) a Simão Pereira (fim trecho urbano) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15461	High impact	0	0	0
1622 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-874 - Entr. p/ Simão Pereira a divisa MG/RJ (Paraibuna) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15461	High impact	368,396	0	368,396
1797 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-776 - Senhora do Carmo a Itambé do Mato Dentro - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,15459	High impact	0	0	0

Table 3.55: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 6)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
154 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-262 - Arcos	0,15457	High impact	8,085,767	0	8,085,767
1619 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-040 (Barreira do Triunfo) à Entr. MG-353 - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15456	High impact	580,924	0	580,924
1569 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-838 - Entr. BR-262 a Luisburgo - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15456	High impact	4,224,730	0	4,224,730
1475 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116-Sobralia a Fernandes Tourinho - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15454	High impact	55,119	0	55,119
1653 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-602 - final perímetro urbano Taiobeiras a início perímetro urbano São João do Paraíso - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,15453	High impact	7,759,182	0	7,759,182
1221 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-265 - Entr. BR-116/356 (Muriaé) à Entr. BR-120(A) (Guidoval) - 5ª CRG - Ubá	0,15451	High impact	1,543,157	0	1,543,157
1458 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-678 - Novo Cruzeiro à Entr. MG-211 - 22ª CRG - Araçuaí	0,15451	High impact	0	0	0
1698 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-720 - São Sebastião do Maranhão à Entr. MG-C120 - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15450	High impact	1,411,604	0	1,411,604
1651 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-674 - Entr. BR-365 a Ponto Chique - 33ª CRG - Pirapora	0,15450	High impact	3,221,898	0	3,221,898
1637 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-497 - Entr. BR-364(B) à div. MG/MS (Rio Paranaíba) - 31ª CRG - Ituiutaba	0,15448	High impact	7,602,606	0	7,602,606
1126 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Ribeirão Sarzedo à Entr. Av. Inhotim - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15440	High impact	85,079	0	85,079
1611 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-285 - divisa RJ/MG à Entr. BR-116 (Laranjal) - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15439	High impact	1,072,825	0	1,072,825
1654 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-623 - Ninheira a São João do Paraíso (início Pontilhão) - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,15435	High impact	1,271,489	0	1,271,489
695 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Jordânia - Almenara	0,15435	High impact	8,704,159	0	8,704,159
1695 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-120 - Entr. MG-308 (Capelinha) à Entr. p/ M dos Homens (div. 38/2 CRG) - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15434	High impact	3,628,374	0	3,628,374
1729 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116 (Caratinga) a Aeroporto de Ubaporanga - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15432	High impact	405,144	0	405,144
1277 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-040 à Entr. Avenida Tancredo Neves/Rua I - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15430	High impact	0	0	0
1269 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-164 - Entr. BR-040 a final perímetro urbano Felixlândia (Córrego do Bagre) - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15430	High impact	0	0	0
1260 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-214 - Senador M.Gonçalves (div. 38/8 CRG) à Entr. MGC-367 - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,15422	High impact	1,122,251	0	1,122,251
214 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Funil (km 44) – Brumadinho (km 50,2)	0,15403	High impact	795,742	0	795,742
1804 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-436 - Entr. BR-381 a início do trecho urbano (Barão de Cocais) (km 16,2) - 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,15402	High impact	1,333,257	0	1,333,257
1692 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-603 - Januária a início Terra Indígena Xacriabá - 37ª CRG - Januária	0,15398	High impact	3,181,420	0	3,181,420
1564 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-342 - Entr. BR-116(B)/418/MG-217 (Teófilo Otoni) a Ouro Verde de Minas - 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,15397	High impact	3,590,920	0	3,590,920
1522 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-262 a Veríssimo - 25ª CRG - Uberaba	0,15390	High impact	1,393,300	0	1,393,300
153 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Guarda Mor - Coromandel	0,15386	High impact	11,846,290	0	11,846,290
1294 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-452 - Entr. BR-153(B) à Entr. BR-365(A) (Xapetuba) - 11ª CRG - Uberlândia	0,15380	High impact	8,986,537	0	8,986,537

Table 3.56: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 7)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1662 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-624 - Entr. LMG-635 à Entr. LMG-602 (p/ Taiobeiras) - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,15380	High impact	474,499	0	474,499
1228 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-451 - Entr. BR-135 (Bocaiúva) a Rio Jequitinhonha - 6ª CRG - Montes Claros	0,15378	High impact	7,879,271	0	7,879,271
1340 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-847 - Entr. BR-146 (São Pedro da União) à Entr. MG-446 - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,15374	High impact	767,093	0	767,093
1636 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-497 - Entr. BR-153 (Prata) à Entr. BR-364(A) (Campina Verde) - 31ª CRG - Ituiutaba	0,15371	High impact	2,674,513	0	2,674,513
1332 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-060 - São Gonçalo do Abaeté (DIV 35/14 CRG) à Entr. BR-365 - 14ª CRG - Patos de Minas	0,15357	High impact	1,336,330	0	1,336,330
409 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MGC-383 (p/ Cristina) - Entr. MGC-460 (Carmo de Minas)	0,15357	High impact	2,258,880	0	2,258,880
1685 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-479 - Entr. MG-202(B) (Farofão) à div. MG/GO - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,15353	High impact	979,859	0	979,859
1290 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-267 a Aiuruoca - 10ª CRG - Varginha	0,15352	High impact	337,764	0	337,764
1514 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-810 - Entr. BR-262 p/ Campo Florido a Pirajuba - 25ª CRG - Uberaba	0,15351	High impact	1,104,736	0	1,104,736
1639 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-510 - contorno de Jaíba à Entr. MG-401 à Entr. MG-401 B - 32ª CRG - Janaúba	0,15347	High impact	675,951	0	675,951
1746 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-020 - Bairro Pinhões à Entr. p/ Taquaraçu de Minas - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15346	High impact	1,563,786	0	1,563,786
1679 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-638 - Uruana a Garapuava - 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,15346	High impact	286,849	0	286,849
1849 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-350 - perímetro urbano São Sebastião do Rio Verde B a fim perímetro urbano São Sebastião do Rio Verde - 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,15344	High impact	0	0	0
1812 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-146/491 a Juruiaia - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,15344	High impact	411,980	0	411,980
1587 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-265 a Divino - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15340	High impact	117,288	0	117,288
1264 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-010 (Serro) a Alvorada de Minas - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,15340	High impact	850,679	0	850,679
1688 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-605 - Entr. BR-135 (Norte) à Entr. BR-135 (Sul) - 37ª CRG - Januária	0,15339	High impact	1,208,130	0	1,208,130
1375 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-829 - Entr. MG-262 a Barra Longa - 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,15337	High impact	608,380	0	608,380
1560 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116 a Itambacuri - 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,15336	High impact	561,733	0	561,733
1130 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Prudente de Moraes (Cemitério) a final perímetro urbano Funilândia - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15332	High impact	590,422	0	590,422
414 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MG-408 - Entr. BR-040 (km 165 ao 215,6)	0,15329	High impact	6,494,282	0	6,494,282
169 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-135 - Morro da Garça	0,15322	High impact	1,861,009	0	1,861,009
383 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-365 p/Patrocínio - Entr. MG-187 (Div. 07/18 URG) - Entr. BR-146 p/Serra do Salitre	0,15317	High impact	5,454,684	0	5,454,684
1421 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-460 (Toledo) à div. MG/SP (Pedra Bela) - 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,15317	High impact	48,032	0	48,032
1786 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-383 - início perímetro urbano São Lourenço à Entr. BR-460 (São Lourenço) - 10ª CRG - Varginha	0,15317	High impact	4,115,289	0	4,115,289
1881 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-252 - Entr. MG-164 (B) (p/ Sto.A.Monte) à Entr. MG-170 (Moema) - 20ª CRG - Formiga	0,15316	High impact	0	0	0

Table 3.57: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 8)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1192 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-040 a Santana dos Montes - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15316	High impact	956,747	0	956,747
1693 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-603 - final Terra Indígena Xacriabá a Miravânia - 37ª CRG - Januária	0,15315	High impact	757,637	0	757,637
1272 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. CMG-135 a Santa Bárbara - 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15309	High impact	1,952,668	0	1,952,668
1626 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-226 - Entr. BR-153 (p/ Centralina) a Ipiacu - 31ª CRG - Ituiutaba	0,15306	High impact	2,900,024	0	2,900,024
1570 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-852 - Entr. BR-262 a Santa Margarida - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15306	High impact	1,368,772	0	1,368,772
1259 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-010 - Entr. BR-259 A a Serra Azul de Minas (fim do trecho pavimentado) - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,15298	High impact	989,335	0	989,335
1697 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na CMG-451 - Entr. BR-367(B) à Entr. MG-117/214 (Itamarandiba) - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15296	High impact	4,318,702	0	4,318,702
1393 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-738 - Entr. MG-188 (Coromandel) - (Rotatória) a final perímetro urbano Coromandel - 18ª CRG - Monte Carmelo	0,15296	High impact	0	0	0
1567 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-615 - Antônio Prado de Minas a Barão do Monte Alto - 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,15294	High impact	1,496,925	0	1,496,925
1178 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-423 - Entr. BR-262 à Entr. BR-352 A (Brumado) - 3ª CRG - Pará de Minas	0,15291	High impact	1,779,322	0	1,779,322
1470 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-775 - Entr. LMG-766 (p/BR-116) a Tumiritinga - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15290	High impact	1,414,679	0	1,414,679
1703 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-217 - Malacacheta (div. 28/38 CRG) à Entr. BR-120 (Água Boa) - 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,15288	High impact	2,146,378	0	2,146,378
1608 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-866 - Andrelândia (Entr. BR-494) a São Vicente de Minas - 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,15284	High impact	2,406,697	0	2,406,697
1344 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-446 - Nova Resende (div. 24/15 CRG: início pavimentação) à Entr. BR-146/491 (Muzambinho) - 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,15283	High impact	1,122,335	0	1,122,335
1123 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-437 - Entr. MGC-262 (Sabará) à Entr. AMG-0150 (Nova Lima) - 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,15280	High impact	0	0	0
395 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-040 - São Sebastião das Águas Claras	0,15275	High impact	975,425	0	975,425
1661 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-251 a Santa Cruz de Salinas (início perímetro urbano) - 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,15273	High impact	537,868	0	537,868
1823 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-270 - Entr. MG-C383 (Entre Rios Minas) a Entre Rios Minas - 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,15272	High impact	432,037	0	432,037
1733 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-820 - Entr. BR-262 à Entr. CMG-120 (A) - 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,15267	High impact	69,205	0	69,205
1775 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-735 - Milho Verde a S. Gonçalo do Rio das Pedras - 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,15266	High impact	956,517	0	956,517
1474 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. BR-116 a Sobralia - 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,15263	High impact	285,399	0	285,399
1855 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-891 - Córrego Danta à Entr. BR-354 - 20ª CRG - Formiga	0,15261	High impact	3,909,829	0	3,909,829
1187 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na LMG-844 - Entr. BR-040 a Casa Grande - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15260	High impact	2,202,263	0	2,202,263
1761 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na MG-155 - Jeceaba à Entr. BR-383 - 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,15256	High impact	367,019	0	367,019
1537 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário na AMG-900 - Entr. MG-188 a Guarda-Mor - 26ª CRG - Paracatu	0,15249	High impact	0	0	0
Total	-----	-----	1,006,297,868	0	1,006,297,868

Table 3.58: RodoPub1 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 9)

RodoPub2 Portfolio: Road projects contract awarded or under procurement, for implementation monitoring

Table 3.59 displays the projects in the RodoPub2¹⁶ portfolio, as illustrated in Figure 3.28. The criteria adopted for selecting projects for this portfolio were:

- **Sector:** Road;
- **Government Level:** State;
- **Status:** Procurement in Progress or contract awarded;
- **Feasibility:** Unevaluated;
- **Impact:** High, medium, or low.

Figure 3.28: Map of Projects in the RodoPub2 Portfolio

¹⁶The RodoPub2 Portfolio included all road maintenance projects, regardless of their impact classification (high, medium, or low).

Impact	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Biennium 25-26 (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
Low impact	12	0	66,748,764	43,318,892	66,748,764
Medium impact	64	623,539,948	67,431,481	244,794,996	690,971,429
High impact	36	75,512,260	85,789,555	65,444,740	161,301,816
Total	112	699,052,209	219,969,801	353,558,629	919,022,010

Table 3.59: Projects in the RodoPub2 Portfolio by Impact

Due to the size of the RodoPub2 portfolio, the classification results were divided by primary intervention, as indicated in Table 3.60, which will be detailed in the following subsections.

Main Intervention	Projects	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)	Total Investment (%)
Total	0				nan

Table 3.60: Summary by Intervention for the RodoPub2 Portfolio

For the projects listed in Tables 3.61 to 3.65 below, the recommended course of action is to monitor execution with priority.

RodoPub2 Portfolio - Construction of special engineering structures

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
393 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Uberlândia - Contorno Sul Ponte sobre o Rio Uberabinha	0,15753	High impact	2,562,323	0	2,562,323
223 - Implantação de OAE: Couto de Magalhães de Minas - Diamantina	0,15120	High impact	17,297	0	17,297
202 - Alargamento da Ponte sobre Ferrovia da Vale - Caeté-Barão de Cocais e Contorno de Barão de Cocais	0,12308	Medium impact	293,107	0	293,107
385 - Implantação de OAE na LMG-840. Ponte sobre o Rio Matipó e Implantação de Interseção na Rodovia LMG-840, trecho Entr. BR-262 (Padre Fialho) a Pedra Bonita	0,12143	Medium impact	826,077	0	826,077
Total	-----	-----	3,698,806	0	3,698,806

Table 3.61: RodoPub2 Portfolio - Construction of special engineering structures

RodoPub2 Portfolio - Expansion and Construction of Road Sections

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1906 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Contorno de Caeté	0,17392	Medium impact	10,900,324	0	10,900,324
313 - MG 252: Trecho km 87,3 (Entroncamento da MG-170 em Moema) e o km 70 (Entroncamento da MG-252 com a MG-164)	0,16646	Medium impact	981,790	0	981,790
304 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Esmeraldas - São José da Varginha	0,16477	Medium impact	16,139,995	0	16,139,995
294 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Sete Lagoas - Anel Viário (Complementação)	0,16007	Medium impact	572,473	0	572,473
599 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: São Gotardo - Entr. BR-354 (p/ Patos de Minas)	0,15932	Medium impact	8,322,495	0	8,322,495
311 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: LMG-881 - Itamonte - Alagoa	0,15931	Medium impact	1,296,583	0	1,296,583
295 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Uberlândia - Contorno Sul (Complementação)	0,15825	Medium impact	2,743,510	0	2,743,510
593 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MGC-265/MG-452 (p/Paiva) - Entr. BR-040	0,15754	Medium impact	0	0	0
185 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Três Pontas - Varginha	0,15747	Medium impact	8,033,078	0	8,033,078
306 - Pavimentação de trecho rodoviário em estrada vicinal em Canápolis	0,15705	Medium impact	2,726,036	0	2,726,036
598 - Ampliação de trecho rodoviário: Entr. LMG-764 (p/ Matutina) - São Gotardo	0,15543	Medium impact	1,517,967	0	1,517,967
1902 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na MGC-479: Januária - Rio Pardo	0,15407	Medium impact	93,991,120	0	93,991,120
251 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Fronteira dos Vales - Entr. MG-205 (Joáima)	0,15385	Medium impact	5,847,661	0	5,847,661
291 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Serro (Alça Bairro Machadinho)	0,15379	Medium impact	3,664,417	0	3,664,417
252 - Pavimentação de trecho rodoviário: Pintópolis - Uruçuia	0,15351	Medium impact	17,954,996	0	17,954,996
280 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Januária - Tejuco - Pandeiros, na MGC-479	0,15238	Medium impact	14,679,591	0	14,679,591
1904 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na MG-214: Itamarandiba (Entr. BR-451) - Senador Modestino	0,15236	Medium impact	43,289,232	0	43,289,232
201 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Estaca 0 a 1250 - Entre Ribeiros - Paracatu	0,15100	Medium impact	8,771,958	0	8,771,958
1912 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na LMG-626: Curral de Dentro - Mirandópolis	0,14893	Medium impact	39,359,861	0	39,359,861
1903 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na MG-220: Diamantina - Monjolos	0,14891	Medium impact	67,186,503	0	67,186,503
1910 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na LMG-629: Rio Pardo de Minas - Entr. LMG-635 (Mato Verde)	0,14875	Medium impact	34,482,613	0	34,482,613
283 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Minas Novas (Contorno)	0,14861	Medium impact	562,529	0	562,529
597 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MG-410 - Entr. BR-365 (Patos de Minas)	0,14852	Medium impact	0	0	0
363 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Carlos Chagas - Distrito de Presidente Pena	0,14851	Medium impact	905,487	0	905,487
310 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-040 - Morada Nova de Minas	0,14698	Medium impact	16,604,139	0	16,604,139
1901 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na MG-214: Capelinha - Itamarandiba	0,14563	Medium impact	50,057,600	0	50,057,600
1898 - Implantação de trecho rodoviário na LMG-706: Entr. BR-040 - Vazante	0,14358	Medium impact	66,931,277	0	66,931,277
Total	-----	-----	517,523,247	0	517,523,247

Table 3.62: RodoPub2 Portfolio - Expansion and Construction of Road Sections

RodoPub2 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
1092 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 25ª CRG - Uberaba	0,18248	High impact	0	6,206,754	6,206,754
1079 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 12ª CRG - Itabira	0,17606	High impact	0	2,918,923	2,918,923
1094 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 27ª CRG - Pedra Azul	0,17255	High impact	0	2,791,467	2,791,467
1085 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 18ª CRG - Monte Carmelo	0,17118	High impact	0	2,299,508	2,299,508
1104 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 37ª CRG - Januária	0,17003	High impact	0	2,520,935	2,520,935
1100 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 33ª CRG - Pirapora	0,16907	High impact	0	4,657,057	4,657,057
1081 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 14ª CRG - Patos de Minas	0,16837	High impact	0	5,736,034	5,736,034
1106 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 39ª CRG - João Pinheiro	0,16694	High impact	0	8,173,009	8,173,009
1105 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 38ª CRG - Capelinha	0,16572	High impact	0	2,312,087	2,312,087
1101 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 34ª CRG - Salinas	0,16318	High impact	0	870,069	870,069
1098 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 31ª CRG - Ituiutaba	0,16316	High impact	0	1,234,400	1,234,400
1103 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 36ª CRG - Arinos	0,16233	High impact	0	6,944,386	6,944,386
1074 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 7ª CRG - Araxá	0,16228	High impact	0	5,844,247	5,844,247
174 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Congonhas do Norte - Ouro Fino - Conceição do Mato Dentro	0,16021	High impact	15,699,028	0	15,699,028
1076 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 9ª CRG - Curvelo	0,15961	High impact	0	8,317,720	8,317,720
1088 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 21ª CRG - Jequitinhonha	0,15721	High impact	0	6,063,437	6,063,437
209 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. Divisa BA/MG - Teófilo Otoni - Subtrecho Divisa BA/MG - km 87 (Lote 1) / Nanuque - Divisa MG/ES	0,15659	High impact	7,899,875	0	7,899,875
171 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-050 - Entr. MG-190 e Acesso a Conquista	0,15641	High impact	3,517,292	0	3,517,292
381 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Nova Porteirinha - Janaúba - Entr. BR-251 e Entr. MGC-122 - Capitão Enéas	0,15597	Medium impact	14,440,797	0	14,440,797
172 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. BR-040 - Pompéu, Pompéu - Agropéu e Abaeté - Entr. LMG-793	0,15551	High impact	4,988,498	0	4,988,498
366 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Bonfinópolis de Minas - Natalândia	0,15497	High impact	71,970	0	71,970
244 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Águas Formosas - Pavão	0,15464	High impact	3,270,170	0	3,270,170
178 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Paracatu - Guarda Mor	0,15448	Medium impact	4,743,350	0	4,743,350
181 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. Divisa BA/MG - Teófilo Otoni - subtrecho km 87 - km 178,3 (lote 2) / Ataleia - Entr. BR-418	0,15434	High impact	9,131,111	0	9,131,111
245 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Pavão - Entr. BR-116 (p/ Teófilo Otoni)	0,15429	Medium impact	12,507,153	0	12,507,153
188 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MGC-455 (Pirajuba) - Frutal, Campo Florido - Pirajuba e Trevo de Pirajuba	0,15391	High impact	1,869,787	0	1,869,787

Table 3.63: RodoPub2 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 1)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
293 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Serro (MG-010 Dep. Augusto Clementino)	0,15344	Medium impact	2,690,622	0	2,690,622
179 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entrº BR-262 (Araxá) - Div. MG/SP	0,15329	High impact	12,880,680	0	12,880,680
292 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Serro (Contorno Sul)	0,15323	Medium impact	1,963,666	0	1,963,666
1093 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 26ª CRG - Paracatu	0,15306	High impact	0	976,833	976,833
382 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Martinho Campos - Bom Despacho e Entr. BR-352 - Albert Isaacson	0,15264	High impact	7,511,539	0	7,511,539
1102 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 35ª CRG - Abaeté	0,15193	High impact	0	5,524,019	5,524,019
384 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Conceição do Mato Dentro - Serro	0,15142	Medium impact	8,987,618	0	8,987,618
166 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Bom Jesus do Galho - Entr. BR-116 (Caratinga) e São Sebastião do Anta - Inhapim	0,15049	Medium impact	3,498,912	0	3,498,912
301 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: MG-329/ LMG-823 (Bom Jesus do Galho a Entr. BR-116 (Caratinga) e São Sebastião do Anta a Inhapim)	0,15049	Medium impact	3,498,912	0	3,498,912
1078 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 11ª CRG - Uberlândia	0,14972	High impact	0	8,550,609	8,550,609
375 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Aracitaba - Entr. MG-452 (p/ Oliveira Fortes) e Paiva - Oliveira Fortes	0,14962	Medium impact	3,802,786	0	3,802,786
163 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Dom Silvério - Ponte Nova e Sem Peixe - Entr. MGC-120	0,14927	Medium impact	3,414,328	0	3,414,328
483 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Cássia - Divisa MG/SP	0,14920	Medium impact	22,984,511	0	22,984,511
157 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Nacip Raydan - Virgolândia	0,14902	Medium impact	789,092	0	789,092
182 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Viçosa - Porto Firme	0,14895	Medium impact	1,109,722	0	1,109,722
173 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Porto Firme - Guaraciaba	0,14791	Medium impact	2,154,050	0	2,154,050
161 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Lajinha - Mutum	0,14760	Medium impact	3,001,319	0	3,001,319
176 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MGC-464 (Sacramento) - Entr. BR-262	0,14743	Medium impact	2,917,679	0	2,917,679
175 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Entr. MG-030 - Raposos	0,14694	Medium impact	856,363	0	856,363
159 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Itabirinha - Mendes Pimentel	0,14637	Medium impact	2,221,493	0	2,221,493
160 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Goiabeira - Entr. BR-259	0,14603	Medium impact	2,246,612	0	2,246,612
213 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Condomínio Capela - Início Perímetro Urbano de Ribeirão das Neves (Trevo Cirin)	0,14571	Medium impact	1,391,105	0	1,391,105
1089 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 22ª CRG - Araçuaí	0,14505	High impact	0	2,380,804	2,380,804
152 - Manutenção de trecho rodoviário: Indianópolis - Entr. BR-365	0,14476	Medium impact	1,844,304	0	1,844,304
158 - Manutenção de trechos rodoviários: Pescador - Nova Módica e Nova Módica - São José do Divino	0,14256	Medium impact	3,833,112	0	3,833,112
358 - Manutenção de OAE: Entr. BR-262 - Entr. MG-265 (p/ Pedra Bonita)	0,13968	Medium impact	0	310,609	310,609

Table 3.64: RodoPub2 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 2)

Project	CI	Impact	CAPEX (\$)	OPEX (\$)	Total Investment (\$)
367 - Manutenção de OAE: Entr. Cana Brava - Entr. MG-181	0,13626	Medium impact	0	256,651	256,651
365 - Manutenção de OAE: Entr. BR-040 - Porto Buriti	0,13626	Medium impact	0	477,834	477,834
255 - Manutenção de OAE: Entr. Mercês - Rio Pomba e Rio Pomba - Tabuleiro	0,13560	Medium impact	0	1,290,629	1,290,629
361 - Manutenção de OAE: Inhotim Viaduto II (Acesso)	0,12754	Medium impact	0	743,735	743,735
1097 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 30ª CRG - Juiz de Fora	0,12584	High impact	0	1,467,249	1,467,249
1068 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 1ª CRG - Belo Horizonte	0,10551	Medium impact	0	17,109,555	17,109,555
1072 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 5ª CRG - Ubá	0,10052	Medium impact	0	9,442,657	9,442,657
1086 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 19ª CRG - Itajubá	0,09727	Medium impact	0	8,969,461	8,969,461
1083 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 16ª CRG - Oliveira	0,09717	Medium impact	0	8,108,487	8,108,487
1070 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 3ª CRG - Pará de Minas	0,09287	Medium impact	0	7,004,086	7,004,086
1077 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 10ª CRG-Varginha	0,09118	Medium impact	0	9,214,625	9,214,625
1107 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 40ª CRG - Coronel Fabriciano	0,08888	Medium impact	0	2,258,402	2,258,402
1096 - Conservação dos trechos rodoviários da 29ª CRG - Manhumirim	0,08318	Medium impact	0	2,244,744	2,244,744
1082 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 15ª CRG - Poços de Caldas	0,08178	Low impact	0	8,437,697	8,437,697
1091 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 24ª CRG - Passos	0,08044	Low impact	0	1,197,774	1,197,774
1071 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 4ª CRG - Barbacena	0,07994	Low impact	0	7,775,936	7,775,936
1095 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 28ª CRG - Teófilo Otoni	0,07524	Low impact	0	6,557,266	6,557,266
1084 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 17ª CRG - Ponte Nova	0,07524	Low impact	0	1,718,784	1,718,784
1080 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 13ª CRG - Brasília de Minas	0,07376	Low impact	0	6,265,363	6,265,363
1099 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 32ª CRG - Janaúba	0,07322	Low impact	0	2,721,552	2,721,552
1087 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 20ª CRG - Formiga	0,07301	Low impact	0	1,443,589	1,443,589
1069 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 2ª CRG - Guanhães	0,07030	Low impact	0	9,021,298	9,021,298
1090 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 23ª CRG - Governador Valadares	0,06664	Low impact	0	6,562,396	6,562,396
1073 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 6ª CRG - Montes Claros	0,06543	Low impact	0	6,227,752	6,227,752
1075 - Conservação dos Trechos Rodoviários da 8ª CRG - Diamantina	0,05433	Low impact	0	8,819,350	8,819,350
Total	-----	-----	171,737,471	219,969,801	391,707,272

Table 3.65: RodoPub2 Portfolio - Maintenance of Special Engineering Structures and Road Sections (Part 3)

Conclusion

The positive impacts of adopting a robust planning methodology for infrastructure projects are substantial. The recommended Short-Term PELT portfolio comprises 512 projects encompassing 851 municipalities in Minas Gerais, covering approximately 99% of the State's territory and totalling \$ 95 billion, of which \$ 51 billion is CAPEX and \$ 44 billion is OPEX. Of these, 164 projects are already under contract or in execution, while the remaining 348 projects have varying recommended indications for managerial decision-making, depending on the managerial portfolio to which each project has been assigned.

Considering the direct impacts of the projects to be prioritised, social and economic benefits exceeding \$ 247 billion are estimated for Minas Gerais by 2055, driven by infrastructure development. Given the scale of these figures, the greatest benefit of this initiative is that it provides decision-makers with solid, defensible, and transparent guidance. Any public or private investment decision has significant implications for transport costs, travel times, emissions, and other factors, underscoring the importance of appropriate methods for investment prioritisation. Consequently, contracts and business deals arising from projects that have undergone such an evaluation and strategic planning process not only begin with robust data for structuring but are also more readily accepted by the market.

Thus, the results presented here serve as a key supporting tool to guide short-term decision-making on logistics and transport infrastructure investments in the State of Minas Gerais.

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